

Oper8 NNs, including NNOs activities

WP1: Establishment and governance of the Oper8 thematic network

D 1.2: Oper8 NNs, including NNOs activities (Version 1)

Authors: Francisco Javier Rodríguez-Rigueiro, Camille Guilbert, Lynn Tatnell, Kevin Godfrey, Viktoria Zagorska, Lorenzo Tramacere, Thomas Börjesson, Ilias Travlos, Nicoleta Darra, Olga Kriezi and María Rosa Mosquera-Losada

Table of content

Document Information	1
Document history	2
Abbreviations	3
Participants	4
Document summary	5
Document content	6
<i>Part. 1 Introduction</i>	<i>6</i>
<i>Part. 2 Oper8 National Networks settlement</i>	<i>6</i>
2.1 National Networks.....	6
2.2 National Network Operators.....	7
2.3 Physical Training Session	7
2.3.1 Preparatory activities.....	8
2.3.2 Attendees	8
2.3.3 Agenda.....	9
2.3.4 Training activities (Physical Training Session summary and outcomes)	9
2.4 Oper8 activities with NNOs playing a pivotal role	14
2.4.1 Needs, barriers and Gaps questionnaire	14
2.4.2 Focus group meetings	15
2.4.3 Demo Farm Events.....	16
2.4.4 Cross-visit events	16
2.4.5 Literature Review/Projects review.....	17
<i>Part. 3 NNOs activity in year 1</i>	<i>18</i>
3.1.1 Spain.....	18
3.1.2 Greece.....	18
3.1.3 France.....	20
3.1.4 Italy.....	21
3.1.5 Sweden.....	22
3.1.6 Latvia	23
3.1.7 The UK.....	24
3.1.8 Lessons learnt and problematics faced	25
<i>Part. 4 Conclusion</i>	<i>27</i>
<i>ANNEX 1</i>	<i>28</i>

Document Information

Project Acronym	OPER8
Project Title	European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control
EU Project Officer	Celine Choquer
Project Coordinator	Spyros Fountas
Project Duration	October 2022 - September 2025 (36 months)
Deliverable No	1.2
Dissemination Level	PU ¹
Work Package	WP1: Establishment and governance of the Oper8 thematic network
Task	T1.2
Lead Beneficiary	USC
Lead Author	María Rosa Mosquera-Losada and Francisco Javier Rodríguez-Rigueiro
Co - Authors	Camille Guilbert, Lynn Tatnell, Kevin Godfrey, Ilias Travlos, Nicoleta Darra, Olga Kriezi, Viktoria Zagorska, Lorenzo Tramacere and Thomas Börjesson
Due Date of Deliverable	September 30, 2023.
Actual Submission Date	September 30, 2023.

TABLE 1: DOCUMENT INFORMATION

¹ PU = public | PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services) | RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) | CO= Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1	14/09/2023	Draft	First Draft	USC
2	20/09/2023	Draft	Internal review	IFV and ADAS
3	26/09/2023	Draft	Drafting after review	USC and AUA
4	29/09/2023	Final version	Final version	USC
5	30/09/2023	Final version	Submission	USC

TABLE 2: DOCUMENT HISTORY

Abbreviations

IWM	INTEGRATED WEED MANAGEMENT
NN(S)	NATIONAL NETWORK(S)
NNO(S)	NATIONAL NETWORK OPERATOR(S)
OG(S)	OPERATIONAL GROUP
PA	PRACTICE ABSTRACT
FG	FOCUS GROUP

TABLE 3: ABBREVIATIONS

Participants

Participants		Contact
Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) Greece		Prof. Spyros Fountas sfountas@aual.gr
University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) Spain		MOSQUERA LOSADA MARIA ROSA mrosa.mosquera.losada@usc.es
University of Pisa (UNIPi) Italy		Daniele Antichi daniele.antichi@unipi.it
Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies (LLU) Latvia		Jānis Jaško janis.jasko@llu.lv
SK ADAS LTD (ADAS) UK		Lynn Tatnell, Will John Lynn.Tatnell@adas.co.uk will.john@adas.co.uk
AGROVÄST Livsmedel AB (AGROVAST) Sweden		Thomas Börjesson thomas.borjesson@agrovast.se
Institut Français de la Vigne et du Vin (IFV) France		Eirios Hugo, Camille Guilbert eirios.hugo@vignevin.com camille.guilbert@vignevin.com
Farmers Parliament (ZSA) Latvia		Inga Berzina inga@zemniekusaeima.lv
Organic Research Centre (ORC) UK		Matt Smees, Julia Cooper matt.s@organicresearchcentre.com julia.c@organicresearchcentre.com
AGROMET P.C. (AGROMET) Greece		Aris Zamidis azamidis@tractorgps.gr

TABLE 4: PARTICIPANTS

Document summary

The Horizon 2020 initiative Oper8 comprises of a thematic network dedicated to advancing alternative weed control practices in seven European countries. Within this network, eight Operational Groups (OGs) have been gathered/formed, serving as the foundation for Oper8's activities. The Oper8 project aims to create a well-balanced, multi-actor thematic network spanning the EU, uniting these OGs to harness their collective potential. Together, they will engage with key actors in the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) to share knowledge and technical outputs, and expand their impact within the EU's agricultural landscape, fostering the development of resilient farming systems. Oper8's approach comprises essential AKIS stakeholders such as farmers, advisors, researchers, and industry representatives seeking to connect OGs, foster collaborative analysis and adaptation, scaling solutions to a European level, and promoting a shift towards IWM practices.

As part of the project, this deliverable provides an insightful overview of the activities undertaken by the National Network Operators (NNOs) within the Oper8 project within year one. The primary focus of this report is to provide an in-depth analysis, following the evaluation criteria set in D1.1 for the NNs-NNOs' progress, allowing the annual assessment of the activities held within the Oper8 Network.

In this report, an analysis of the performance of NNs-NNOs activities within Oper8 during its inaugural year has been performed, with a specific focus on the National Network Operators (NNOs). These experienced innovation drivers have played a central role in generating cross-fertilization, information gathering, national dynamic, target group reaching, internal discussion to expand Oper8 network and impact. Within this report, Oper8 activities orchestrated by NNOs will be scrutinised, including the Needs, Barriers and Gaps survey, focus group meetings, Demo Farm events, cross-visits, and literature review.

Document content

Part. 1 Introduction

The Oper8 project, rooted in the accomplishments of eight (8) OGs spanning Europe, endeavours to reshape herbicide-based weed control practices by advocating for sustainable, non-chemical alternatives. Keystone to this mission is the establishment of stakeholder engagement processes designed to develop, create and maintain National Networks (NNs) within each partner country. Based on this premise, seven (7) NNs were created following the guidelines provided in D1.1, accounting with a responsible member (NNOs) linked to the other OGs' NNOs and forming the foundation of Oper8. Each NN was based on one OG and one NNO, except for the UK having two NNOs due to two OGs. The Oper8 NNOs will provide support and boost project activities seeking to widening the adoption of non-chemical weed control techniques, as torchbearers of this progress entrusted with the pivotal role of orchestrating these efforts.

This report aims to provide a comprehensive examination of the initiatives undertaken by the National Network Operators (NNOs) during the pivotal first year of the Oper8 project. These endeavours encompass a range of activities, including but not limited to:

1. The Physical Training Session (T1.1) for NNOs.
2. Implementation of the Needs, Barriers, and Gaps questionnaire (T2.1), through initial review and broadcasting of the final version in each country.
3. Organization of Focus Group Meetings with experts to validate and expand on the findings from the T2.1 survey.
4. Coordination of Demo Farm events in each country.
5. Supporting Cross-visit activities, as with providing participants and experts, and communicating about the event, designed to disseminate successful strategies related to IWM.
6. Collaborative execution of a comprehensive Literature Review process for T2.2, with a particular emphasis on Solutions & Technologies.
7. The assembly of a panel of experts, not solely for the purpose of conducting Focus Group Meetings but also to attend one day of the Annual Consortium Meeting to be held in Pisa at the end of the project's year one (October 2023).

Considering that the Oper8 project's resolute commitment to sustainable weed control is underscored by collaborative synergy, pioneering solutions, and an unwavering dedication to transformative change, this report serves as a meticulous appraisal of the accomplishments of the NNOs during the initial year. Thus, it is intended to gauge the performance and insights on the effectiveness of these activities and lay the groundwork for forthcoming assessments.

Part. 2 Oper8 National Networks settlement

2.1 National Networks

The Oper8 project has brought together seven (7) Oper8 National Networks (NNs) representing Spain, Greece, Latvia, Italy, France, Sweden, and the UK. These NNs have been formed by integrating existing or future eight partner OGs and engaging, through their activities, diverse stakeholders from multiple distinct target groups, including farmers, advisors, the agri-food industry, the research community, policymakers, citizens and consumers, as well as the EIP-AGRI and CAP networks.

At the core of Oper8's mission is the establishment of these NNs to facilitate policy dialogue and engagement with these target groups, focusing on innovative and sustainable weed control practices. To guide the formation and operation of the NNs, Oper8 adheres to a set of guiding principles. These principles underpin the flexibility, co-construction, multi-level interactions, impartiality, and transparency that characterize the NNs' activities.

Considering the eight OGs previously mentioned, the seven NNs were established as displayed in Table 5, as a first step for choosing NNOs.

Operational Group	NN Country
Experimental cover crops under the rows of grapevines and fruit trees	France
Development of robotized weed control platform	Latvia
Non-chemical weed control in vineyard	Italy
Development of an innovative weed system	Greece
Site specific herbicide applications	Sweden
Ecological control of adventitious plants in agricultural crops	Spain
Camera guided mechanical weeding in field vegetables	UK
Electrical Weed Control	

TABLE 5. OPERATIONAL GROUPS LINKED TO THEIR RESPECTIVE NATIONAL NETWORK WITHIN THE OPER8 PROJECT

2.2 National Network Operators

The Oper8 National Networks (NNs) potential success rely on capable leaders tagged as National Network Operators (NNOs) to guide their activities within partner countries. These NNOs were carefully chosen from among our partner staff members.

Regarding the coordination of NNs, individuals with a wide expertise in the field and a deep understanding of Oper8's objectives were designated as NNOs. Thus, these innovation drivers are now responsible for steering the activities documented in D1.1 in their respective NNs and are instrumental in advancing the project's mission.

To ensure the chosen NNOs were well-prepared to lead their NNs effectively, a dedicated Physical Training Session was planned as part of Task 1.2. This training aimed at equipping and supporting NNOs with the necessary knowledge and tools for successful stakeholder engagement and involvement. Table 6 presents an overview of the selected NNOs, including their names, partner affiliations, and contact details. These individuals are at the forefront of Oper8's efforts to identify and boost IWM practices.

Partner	NNO Name	Contact	NN
IFV	Camille Guilbert	camille.guilbert@vignevin.com	France
ZSA-LLU	Viktoria Zagorska	viktoria.zagorska@llu.lv	Latvia
UNIFI	Lorenzo Tramacere	lorenzo.tramacere@unipi.it	Italy
AUA-AGROMET	Ilias Travlos	travlos@aia.gr	Greece
AGROVAST	Thomas Börjesson	thomas.borjesson@agrovast.se	Sweden
USC	María Rosa Mosquera Losada	mrosa.mosquera.losada@usc.es	Spain
ADAS	Kevin Godfrey	kevin.godfrey@adas.co.uk	UK
ADAS	Lynn Tatnell	lynn.tatnell@adas.co.uk	

TABLE 6. NATIONAL NETWORK OPERATORS OF THE OPER8 PROJECT

2.3 Physical Training Session

As previously mentioned, at the early stages of the Oper8 project, a transformative event unfolded in the days 1 and 2 of February (M05): the dedicated Physical Training Session. This carefully designed session was a pivotal moment, marking a

significant stride towards achieving the final goal of redefining sustainable weed control practices by means of strong and proactive NNs.

The essence of this Physical Training Session was to provide the Oper8 selected NNOs with insights into how to engage stakeholders and boost participation. The presented tools are vital for fostering meaningful interactions and partnerships within their respective NNs. Beyond the acquisition of practical knowledge and adoption of strategies, the session provided opportunity for dynamic discussions. NNOs convened to explore the nuanced dimensions of their roles within the Oper8 ecosystem. Multiple NNOs' questions allowed fruitful discussions and helped the group to understand in depth Oper8 tasks expectations and way to fulfil to it. They delved into strategies for effectively catalysing change and harnessing collective wisdom.

As we delve into this section, we shed light on the objectives, outcomes, and significance of this critical training session, underlining its role in empowering NNs to lead and inspire change in the realm of sustainable weed control.

2.3.1 Preparatory activities

The NNs Physical Training Session was held at the University of Santiago, Campus of Lugo facilities (Galicia – NW Spain). The organization of the Oper8 Physical Training Session needed some preparatory activities in addition to the logistics.

Prior to the meeting, an agenda was circulated to NNs as well as information on the different activities of the session including the field trip part of the training.

The USC staff, as organizers and task leaders, prepared several presentations linked to the activities that NNs were due to carry out i) Preparing online surveys, ii) Workshop preparatory activities, iii) Running workshops and vi) Reporting and NN interactions. In addition, Nicoleta Darra (AUA) as project manager and responsible for D1.1, prepared the presentation of the NNs Guidelines. Each NNO prepared two short presentations referring to their respective OG and NN challenges and potential actors.

2.3.2 Attendees

Organisation	Attendees
AUA	Nicoleta Darra (online)
	Ilias Travlos
	Kiki Kontogeorgou
ZSA	Inga Berzina
ADAS	Kevin Godfrey
	Lynn Tatnell
UNIFI	Lorenzo Tramacere
IFV	Camille Guilbert
AGROVAST	Mats Emilson (online)
USC	María Rosa Mosquera Losada
	Nuria Ferreiro Domínguez
	Julian Díaz Berrios
	Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro

TABLE 7. ATTENDEES TO THE PHYSICAL TRAINING MEETING IN LUGO, INCLUDING NNs AND PARTNERS STAFF

A total of 13 participants attended the meeting including the NNs and other staff supporting NN activities within the Oper8 project. As can be observed, all NNs attended the meeting in person with the exception of Kevin Godfrey who attended online and Thomas Börjesson who was replaced by Mats Emilson (CEO of AGROVAST). Mats delivered the presentations and received the training in order to fulfil the knowledge requirements and transfer this to the NNO. The PPT presentations and the minutes

of the meeting were made available to all the NNOs after the meeting. It should be highlighted that Latvia recently switched NNO, with Inga Berzina being replaced by Viktorija Zagorska as head of the Latvian NN in month 10.

2.3.3 Agenda

The Physical Training Session was split in two days, with day one on theory and presentations, and day two for the demo farm events training methodology including field visits to a couple of IWM experiments that the USC is carrying out in the region of Galicia.

All the presentations of the Physical Training Session are included in Annex 1.

Time	Session	Leading Partner
09:00 – 09:20	Welcome & Introduction	USC
09:20 – 11:00	Guidelines presentation + group discussion	AUA
Coffee Break		
11:30 – 12:00	How to prepare an online survey?	USC
12:00 – 13:50	OGs overview and results (10 min each) + NNs challenges and potential actors (5 minutes each)	All
Lunch Break		
15:00 – 15:40	Workshop preparatory activities	USC
15:40 – 16:30	Running workshops	USC
Coffee Break		
17:00 – 17:40	Reporting + NN interactions	USC
17:40 – 18:00	Discussion & Wrap Up	All
Dinner		
20:00 – 22:00	Dinner	All

TABLE 8. AGENDA DAY 1

Time	Session	Leading Partner
08:30	Departure point field visits - Bus	USC
09:15 – 11:15	First field visit	
Coffee Break		
12:45 – 14:15	Second field visit	USC
Lunch Break		
17:00 – 17:30	Arrival to Lugo	All

TABLE 9. AGENDA DAY 2

2.3.4 Training activities (Physical Training Session summary and outcomes)

2.3.4.1 Welcome and Introduction

Rosa Mosquera (USC) presented the meeting agenda, underlining the importance of the structured framework for our discussions. This roadmap provided all attendees with a comprehensive understanding of the day's proceedings, ensuring training session objectives were met.

In addition to the agenda, meeting logistics were discussed in detail. Practical considerations, including the details for field trip, were addressed.

2.3.4.2 Guidelines presentation

During the meeting, the project manager of Oper-8 (Nicoleta Darra, AUA) took the lead in guiding us through a comprehensive presentation that laid out the blueprint for constructing the National Networks (NNs). This presentation encompassed various critical aspects, such as the roles of NNs and National Network Operators (NNOs), stakeholder selection, and the overarching framework for Oper8.

This informative presentation included insightful details on survey workshops, systematic reviews, cross-fertilization activities, the Digital Inventory (T2.3), and National Action Plans (T2.4). Additionally, it provided a concise summary of the NNs and European Workshops, underscoring their framework and activities. A key highlight was the transfer of knowledge from Work Package 4 (WP4), which drew from the collective results of all NN activities, encompassing best practices, practice abstracts, videos, Demo Farm Events, and more.

Furthermore, the project manager explained the synthesis of the NNs, spotlighting metrics like the actors reached, minimum requirements for farmers and advisors, and the establishment of essential links with other projects.

The presentation also shed light on the key role of NNOs, outlining their responsibilities according to participant categories. It was revealed that the preparation of deliverables, including scientific articles, would be integral to their tasks. Moreover, the concept of annual NNOs reports (as in this deliverable) was introduced, with the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) being responsible for leading and coordinating responsibilities to compile information about yearly NNOs activities.

Finally, the project manager provided valuable insights into the roles of stakeholders and expert panels, rounding off a comprehensive overview of Oper8's structure and vision.

After this Guidelines presentation, a discussion started with NNOs and the rest of attendees addressing important topics as templates for different documents and project activities such as the Needs, Barriers and Gaps survey and Focus Group Meetings.

2.3.4.3 How to prepare an online survey

Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro (USC) delivered a practice session on preparing online surveys. This session sought to equip the National Network Operators (NNOs) with the requisite skills to conduct surveys effectively, ultimately contributing to the project's overarching objectives. During this session, it was decided that Microsoft Forms would serve as the preferred software for survey creation and data collection. This strategic choice aligns with the project's preparatory activities, aimed at facilitating the organization of the National Network (NN) activities, and their subsequent assessment.

2.3.4.4 Overview of OGs and NNs

The meeting featured a series of insightful presentations by NNOs including Operational Groups (OGs) description and National Networks (NNs) challenges and potential actors, shedding light on their innovative approaches to weed control within the Oper8 project and the challenges that may arise while building up the Oper8 Network through NNs. These presentations, along with others from the meeting, are available in Annex 1 for reference.

1. Spain: Rosa Mosquera initiated the session with a presentation on CONTECAD, a Spanish OG dedicated to exploring alternative weeding methods using plant essential oils in horticultural crops. Spanish NN challenges and potential actors were discussed.
2. Sweden: Mats Emilson provided an overview of the Swedish OG's work, which focuses on weeding solutions utilizing robotics and drones. Data collected from drones is leveraged to create spraying maps for machine sprayers, enhancing precision. Swedish NN challenges and potential actors were discussed.

3. UK - Electrical Weeding OG: Lynn Tatnell presented the Electrical Weeding OG, which employs various treatments on multiple treatment timings to evaluate the effectiveness of electrical treatment in reaching roots of perennial weeds.
4. UK - Robotic Mechanical Weeding OG (Inter-row): Kevin Godfrey discussed the Robotic Mechanical Weeding OG, which employs a software and camera system mounted on a tractor with mechanical weeding tools to perform inter-row weeding. UK NN challenges and potential actors were discussed.
5. Greece: Ilias Travlos introduced the AUA-AGROMET OG, focusing on the transfer of technological advancements to small-scale farms. The OG employs a tractor and digital RGB camera to measure conditions during tractor movement, with software integration as a project component. Greek NN challenges and potential actors were discussed.

FIGURE 1. GREEK OG PRESENTATION PART OF THE NNOS PHYSICAL TRAINING SESSION IN LUGO

6. Italy: Lorenzo Tramacere presented the OG CiRAA from Italy, which aims to revolutionize weed management in perennial crops while safeguarding soil health. Their work spans both conventional and organic farms. Italian NN challenges and potential actors were discussed.
7. France: Camille Guilbert highlighted the French OG's endeavours for intra-row cover crops in viticulture and fruit tree experiments. The French NN, under her guidance, seeks to foster collaboration among various stakeholders, including chambers of agriculture, farmers, cooperatives, researchers, and policymakers, all with a focus on viticulture. French NN challenges and potential actors were discussed.
8. Latvia: Inga Berzina provided insights into the Latvian OG's work, centred around a prototype of a camera-based plant recognition solution. The OG has developed a four-wheeled platform robot for fieldwork, capable of identifying and treating weeds. Latvian NN challenges and potential actors were discussed, and it was highlighted that the objective is to establish a collaborative network to address weed control solutions in alignment with Oper8's overarching goals.

FIGURE 2. DISCUSSION DURING THE NNOS PHYSICAL TRAINING SESSION IN LUGO

These presentations served as valuable contributions, showcasing diverse approaches to weed control within the Oper8 project and fostering a spirit of collaboration and knowledge sharing among partners.

2.3.4.5 Workshop preparatory activities

Rosa Mosquera (USC) delivered the presentation on preparatory activities as key among NNOs responsibilities, marking a well-established and agreed-upon procedure.

One critical point reiterated during the presentation was the paramount importance of timing in delivering the results of the T2.1 survey. This consideration emerged as a key factor for the successful progression of the project. Within this framework, the defined roles of NNOs, in accordance with the Grant Agreement guidelines, took centre stage. Particular emphasis was placed on the necessity of involving multiple stakeholders in each National Network (NN). This multi-faceted approach promises a richer understanding of project dynamics.

An essential facet of project evaluation was underscored with the commitment to produce three deliverables annually, each serving as a comprehensive assessment of NNOs' activities.

The presentation further explored the focus areas of each NN workshop, particularly highlighting the concept of solution selection, a process informed by the findings of the T2.1 survey. It was emphasized that once the T2.1 survey results were available, discussions should revolve around the strategies to engage different sectors within the various NNs, ultimately aiming to generate a total of 80 Best Practices (12 per NN).

The presentation also ventured into the domain of stakeholder selection, a pivotal consideration for the project's success. The project requires the engagement of a minimum of 120 actors in the solution evaluation process, with a minimum requirement of 40 stakeholders per country. Concerns were raised regarding attendance at the second NN workshop, but reassurance was provided based on past experiences and the anticipated value of the results. The criteria for stakeholder selection, meticulously outlined in PowerPoint slides, provided clarity and structure to the process. Additionally, guidelines for crafting agendas were imparted to NNOs, emphasizing the importance of a consistent framework to facilitate result analysis.

Crucial components of preparatory activities, namely the preparatory survey and the NN workshop survey, were presented as indispensable tools for meeting preparation and subsequent reporting, rounding off an insightful and informative presentation on Oper8's preparatory endeavours.

2.3.4.6 Running workshops and reporting

During the last two sessions, led by Javier R. Rigueiro (USC), the Oper8 project gained valuable insights into two essential facets: Running Workshops and Reporting. The delivered presentations unveiled an array of activities designed to invigorate meetings and foster knowledge transfer. Notable among these were techniques such as brainstorming and voting, which promise to inject dynamism into project-related gatherings.

In the realm of reporting, NNOs were introduced to practical tools—a Microsoft Word template and Microsoft Excel table—that will serve as initial drafts for crafting comprehensive national workshop reports. These resources will play a vital role in ensuring that workshop outcomes are effectively documented and communicated.

The discussions following the presentations was marked by a collective recognition of the significance of Agricultural Associations (advisors) and farmers as key groups in the workshop framework. Their involvement and insights are poised to serve as the bedrock for the workshops' success. In addition, Rosa Mosquera proposed a strategic move of presenting the results of the National Action Plans to the European Commission (EC). This step aims to harness the EC's influence in disseminating these outcomes across countries, further amplifying the impact of the Oper8 project.

2.3.4.7 Field trip

On the second day of our meeting, the National Network Operators (NNOs) embarked on informative field trips to Demo Farms, where they gained practical knowledge about sustainable weed control methods and organising these events.

FIGURE 3. NNOs VISITED USC EXPERIMENTAL GREENHOUSES

The first stop was in a vineyard in Portomarín, Lugo. Here, Professor Julián García Berrios (USC) explained herbicide-free ways to manage weeds without using herbicides. One of the techniques highlighted was the use of plastic mulches to block sunlight from reaching the soil.

FIGURE 4. OPER8 NNOs VISITING A VINEYARD TREATED WITH NON-CHEMICAL WEEDING METHODS

After the vineyard, NNOs travelled to Boimorto, A Coruña, where Bosques Naturales S.A. operates. This company specializes in high-quality timber production of walnut and cherry trees. They sought an alternative to glyphosate for ecological and

economic reasons. In collaboration with USC's Silvopasture Research Group, they started an experiment using grazing sheep for weed control. The results were impressive, leading to an increase in sheep numbers, generating income from lamb sales and other products like sheep manure. Even after a decade, the effects of repeated glyphosate use on ground vegetation were evident.

These field trips not only provided practical insights into sustainable weed control but also demonstrated innovative and eco-friendly approaches to farming. Visits were aligned with the goals of the Oper8 project, promoting environmentally conscious agricultural practices and an example on the framework to organize each NN Demo Farm events.

In addition, information on the first NNOs gathering was included on the website of the Oper8 project (<https://www.oper-8.eu/>) as well as posted on the project's social media.

2.3.4.8 Conclusions and agreements

In conclusion, several key agreements and action points emerged from the Physical Training Session meeting held in Lugo:

- The creation and uploading of PA guidelines and a PA template document on the Oper8 platform were deemed essential.
- Feedback from the workshop survey was asked to be provided asap and if possible during March, with comprehensive T2.1 workshop survey analysis set to be ready for circulation within the consortium by May.
- The initial Oper8 workflow for NNOs was established: T2.1 Survey → Focus Group interviews → Creation and development of NNs (with a minimum of 250 AKIS actors reached per country, being 20 farmers and 20 advisors at least).
- A sector-specific approach, focusing on arable crops, permanent crops, and permanent grassland, was agreed upon for searching for solutions.
- Maximizing survey responses, including circulation through social networks like Facebook, was endorsed for the T2.1 survey.
- Microsoft Forms was chosen as the software for survey creation and data collection for preparatory activities related to NN workshops and workshop assessment.
- A WhatsApp group exclusively for NNOs during field visits was proposed and accepted to facilitate efficient communication and discussion among NNOs

2.4 Oper8 activities with NNOs playing a pivotal role

During year one the NNs have been setup according to the methodology developed within the Physical Training Session in Lugo., Several activities planned as part of the Oper8 project were carried out including the pivotal role of the NNOs as innovation drivers connecting stakeholders with the project consortium in a bidirectional flow of information.

The most important activities carried out by NNOs within the Oper8 main objectives in year one were:

- Needs, gaps and barriers questionnaire production, broadcasting, and analysis
- Focus group meetings
- Demo farm events
- Cross visit events
- Literature Review/Projects review

All NNOs actively participated in the process for achieving the expected results as nexus between the project consortium and the NN members as stakeholders.

2.4.1 Needs, barriers and Gaps questionnaire

To understand whether farmers could embrace alternative weed control methods and what might be holding them back, an online survey was conducted as part of T2.1. The aim was to figure out what farmers and related stakeholders need to transition to increase the uptake of alternative weed control solutions. The networking activities of NNOs allowed to reach out to a broad network of contacts, both within and outside the National Networks (NNs), and make sure the survey reached as many people as possible.

As from the work carried out by NNOs on circulating the survey, there was a very high level of participation for the surveys as observed in Table 10.

Participant occupation	Country							Total
	France	Spain	Greece	Sweden	Latvia	Italy	UK	
Farmer	67	31	64	27	91	37	44	361
Non-farmer	37	49	28	24	20	40	66	264
Total	104	88	92	51	111	77	110	625

TABLE 10. NUMBER OF SURVEY RESPONDENTS PER COUNTRY REACHED BY OPER8 NNOs

It was not possible to collect the expected amount of 100 responses in all countries. For some of the countries there was an initial quick survey response but then it slowed down and despite a very large effort by the NNO's it was very difficult to get further surveys complete. The completion deadline for four countries was extended to aim to hit the target, but WP leaders and NNOs had to agree an end date to prevent delaying further deliverables. Partners were however pleased with the quality of the survey responses for all countries.

2.4.2 Focus group meetings

The survey results analysis by NNOs and Oper8 members revealed various challenges that hinder the adoption of alternative weed control methods across Europe and the UK. To gain a deeper understanding of these findings, results were further discussed within each NN, by organizing focus group meeting with various stakeholders. The data collected from the survey and these focus group discussions will be valuable in developing National Action Plans, which will guide the practical use of alternative weed control strategies.

FIGURE 5. SPANISH FG MEETING

After gathering insights from the survey, NNOs proceeded to organize focus group (FG) workshops in their country. Each focus group aimed to have at least 10 participants, ensuring diverse representation from key stakeholders involved in weed management, including farmers, advisors, and policymakers. These workshops served the purpose of analysing the survey results, gaining a deeper understanding of the prevailing context, and pinpointing the unique needs and challenges faced by various cropping systems within each country.

	Country							Total
	France	Spain	Greece	Sweden	Latvia	Italy	UK	
Number of experts	10	13	10	16	13	12	13	87

TABLE 11, NUMBER OF EXPERTS TAKING PART IN THE FOCUS GROUP MEETINGS ORGANIZED BY EACH NNO

As observed in table 11, all FG meetings reached at least the minimum number of experts attending the meeting, to a total of 87.

2.4.3 Demo Farm Events

Demo Farm events were organized by NNOs to reach the KPI of at least two per year and per OG, involving at least 60-70 participants per country and per year (see part 3 of this report for details of each country).

2.4.4 Cross-visit events

The online cross-visits are organized twice a year. They are entitled ‘Webinar on alternative weed-control’, with one specific solution or topic being presented in each webinar. These cross-visits are an open invitation, and their aim is to produce cross-fertilization within Europe, between experts and other relevant stakeholders. The objective is to inform participants of cutting-edge information on alternative weed control solutions. All target groups are invited. Several crops are being addressed, with a combination of trial results, machinery and tool presentations, feedback and experience sharing. The first part of the webinar presents current works and results of Oper8 project, then the next part focuses on the alternative solution of the day. It lasts about 1.5 hours, with presentation and question time, and is in English language. The recording is made available on YouTube, IFV webpage, and Oper8 website afterward the webinar.

NNO and Oper8 members are involved to discuss and suggest presentation contents and topics. WP1 meetings on Wednesdays (once a month), gathering all NNOs, are used to communicate about these webinar cross-visits and inform them about needs, requirements and communication expectations. People interested in presenting their work are then gathered to decide on the final program. Then each NNO is asked to communicate widely about the event, to reach the general KPI of over 115 participants in each webinar, from all-over Europe. Various communication supports are available for them: Oper8 posts on social media they can re-post, flyers with program to forward to their own networks and detailed information they can use for their company communication channels. NNOs invite their experts’ panel and many other stakeholders.

- 1st webinar event – 26 April 2023 – Electrical weeding:

A registration number follow-up was sent 3 times before the webinar on 26 April on Electrical Weeding to encourage them to re-post and invite more people to the event. All NNOs tried various communication channels. 122 people attended (Table 12), exceeding the KPI, what is really encouraging for future webinars. Table 13 presents the target group categories that attended the webinar.

Some NNOs also provided useful comments afterwards, about webinar format and organization for improvements. The duration of presentations and invitation process could then be adapted for the next webinar. Table 12

Operational Group	Registration numbers to the 26/04/2023 Oper8 webinar	Attendees numbers on the 26/04/2023 Oper8 webinar
France	20	7
Greece	31	13
Italy	16	12
Latvia	16	10
Other – Europe	39	23
Other – Non Europe	5	0
Spain	22	11
Sweden	10	10
UK	46	34
Unknown	2	2
TOTAL	207	122

TABLE 12. REGISTRATION AND ATTENDANCE NUMBERS TO THE FIRST OPER8 ONLINE CROSS-VISIT ON 26 APRIL 2023

	Target Group categories attendees									Total
	France	Greece	Italy	Latvia	Other - Europe	Spain	Sweden	UK	unknown	
Advisors/Consulting companies	1	3		1	7	1		6		19
Agri-food industry		2			2	2	2	1		9
Citizens/Consumers		1								1
Farmers/Cooperatives	4		2	4	3	1	1	3		18
Other					2	1	1	2	2	8
Policymakers								5		5
Research community	2	7	10	5	9	6	6	17		62

TABLE 13. TARGET GROUP CATEGORIES OF ATTENDEES, BY COUNTRY, FOR THE OPER8 ONLINE CROSS-VISIT ON 26 APRIL 2023

- **2nd webinar event – 19 October 2023 – Cover crops:**

The second webinar is currently being organized. NNOs have been informed during the last WP1 meetings (during summer) of the upcoming webinar in October, which will present cover crops solutions. Speakers and program have been decided at the last meeting on 07 September 2023. NNO will be urged to communicate about this event as soon as the communication support and registration form are available.

2.4.5 Literature Review/Projects review

Most of NNOs participated in T2.2, even on a voluntary basis, by identifying, collecting and reviewing all the available alternative weed control methods. This included performing a literature review on scientific (search on Scopus) and technical solutions available from EU-funded (via the EU Cordis platform) and national projects (via European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability – EIP-AGRI portal), as well as from EIP-AGRI focus groups' publications.

For proceeding with the literature review, NNOs identified the IWM pillars in which they could provide expertise and performed a two-step analysis of the papers obtained after identifying the keywords for each tactic.

Part. 3 NNOs activity in year 1

3.1.1 Spain

NNOs Activity – Oper8 Year 1 in Spain	
Lugo NNOs Training Session	<p>As part of the responsible team to organize this NNOs training session, Rosa Mosquera prepared several presentations for the different points in the agenda of the meeting as well as delivered several. Rosa Mosquera also presented the OG of Spain concerning the use of essential oils for natural control of weeds. In addition, she delivered the presentation on NN challenges and its potential actors.</p> <p>After arranging the field trip, Rosa Mosquera explained two of the experiments visited as part of the training activities for the upcoming Demo Farm events and contacted Prof. Julian Díaz as an expert to explain in person another experiment in vineyards.</p>
Needs, Barriers and Gaps questionnaire	<p>Rosa Mosquera coordinated the distribution of the Needs, Barriers and Gaps questionnaire in Spain reaching a total of close to 1000 persons reached, clarifying the need of respondents to be directly related with farm weeding and agricultural activities. Thus, the survey was circulated to close to 100 Spanish farmers and other stakeholders linked to the agroforestry project AFINET and agricultural cooperatives, 213 agricultural researchers and professors and 686 agricultural students, many of them also farmers.</p> <p>Spain received feedback from 80 respondents, being close to the expected KPI of 100.</p>
Focus Group Meeting (to validate questionnaire results)	<p>Rosa Mosquera and her team organized the Spanish Focus Group Meeting online, in order to promote and facilitate experts' attendance considering their tight schedules. A total of 15 experts were invited considering that probably several of them could not participate, 13 experts attended therefore reaching the KPI. A presentation to explain the questionnaire results to the FG members and guide the discussion was prepared by Rosa Mosquera as well a report written on the Spanish FG meeting outcomes for feeding the deliverable 2.1.</p>
Demo Farm Events	<p>Two Demo Farm events were performed on 21 and 22 of September in Galicia (NW Spain). Rosa Mosquera drafted the events planning and scheduling as well as invited close to 100 participants. Rosa Mosquera and her team recorded the events and processed the clips for sending it to the responsible partners within the Oper8.</p>
Literature review/ projects review for → Identification and collection of alternative weed control methods and techniques	<p>Rosa Mosquera and her team provided highly valuable input to the Oper8 task 2.2 on a voluntary basis. As part of this task, the Spanish NNO and her team contributed to the Field Soil Management pillar identifying the respective keywords and reviewing 177 entries and 31 papers for the tactics of Liming, Stubble Management and Nutrient placement. In addition, Rosa Mosquera participated on the internal reviewing process of the related deliverable.</p>
Cross visit events (26 April 2023)	<p>As NNO in Spain, Rosa Mosquera invited over 12 experts and farmers for them to attend the Cross Visit held on 26 April 2023 virtually, as part of the Oper8 activities. Experts and farmers from Spain attended the event including the USC professors Julián García Berrios and Nuria Ferreiro Domínguez, expressing their interest in participating in future project activities.</p>
Consortium Meeting Pisa	<p>As main expert from Spain, the Spanish NNO Rosa Mosquera invited Professor Julian Jesús García Berrios to travel to Pisa for participating in the Cross-fertilisation activities of the second day of the Consortium meeting, involving experts and NNOs from all the National Networks and fostering knowledge exchange.</p>

3.1.2 Greece

NNOs Activity – Oper8 Year 1 in Greece	
Lugo NNOs Training Session	<p>On 01-02 February 2023, in Santiago de Compostela, Spain, Ilias Travlos (NNO/AUA) presented the Greek OG solution. He also presented recent research on non-chemical weed control options for perennial cropping systems, i.e., olive groves, orchards, and vineyards. The presentation focused specifically on cover crops and emphasized the role of cover crop diversity, mechanical methods such as mowing and mulching, and</p>

	<p>natural herbicides such as hot foam and pelargonic acid that are appropriate for organic farming. All of the above methods and practices were considered valuable components of mixed Integrated Weed Management (IWM) systems that rely less on herbicides and therefore serve the goals of the European Green Deal.</p> <p>In summary, NNO's to the Lugo Training Session encompassed both the preparation and presentation of PowerPoint materials for our OG as well as challenges related to it, ensuring that the content was clear, informative, and engaging.</p>
<p>Needs, Barriers and Gaps questionnaire</p>	<p>The distribution of the Needs, Barriers, and Gaps questionnaire in Greece, was coordinated by the Greek NNO. In particular, the questionnaire was circulated within the extensive social network of NNO and his team, which they have cultivated over the past decade. This network is diverse, encompassing individuals from various socio-economic backgrounds, including farmers, senior and early-stage researchers, advisors, and stakeholders. In total, the survey garnered feedback from 92 respondents, which came remarkably close to the originally set Key Performance Indicator (KPI) of 100. This outcome was a testament to the effectiveness of the distribution strategy and the strength of the social network in reaching the intended audience and collecting valuable insights for the survey. It showcased the power of collaboration and strategic networking in successfully achieving the research objectives.</p>
<p>Focus Group Meeting (to validate questionnaire results)</p>	<p>On 14 July 2023, NNO and his team organized online focus group meeting in Greece aiming to validate the outcomes of T2.1. The primary objective was to encourage and foster discussions and exchange of insights focused on the topic. A total of 15 people were invited and 10 people participated.</p> <p>Among the notable attendees was Anestis Karkanis, an Assistant Professor specializing in Weed Science at the University of Thessaly. His presence added valuable expertise to the discussions and contributed to the depth of insights generated during the meeting. The NNO prepared a presentation to guide the proceedings and ensure a structured discussion. He explained and analysed the results of the questionnaire to the Focus Group members and to lead the discussion, as well as a report on the results of the Greek Focus Group meeting, which is included in Task 2.1. This presentation served the dual purpose of elucidating and analysing the outcomes of the previously conducted questionnaire, providing a basis for informed discussions. The NNO having the role of presenter and moderator, steered conversations and encouraged participants to delve into pertinent topics.</p> <p>Furthermore, NNO along with the AUA team were responsible for generating a comprehensive report that encapsulated the key findings and outcomes of the Greek Focus Group meeting. This report was an integral part of Deliverable 2.1, contributing vital insights and recommendations for the broader research project.</p>
<p>Demo Farm Events</p>	<p>The National Nature Organization (NNO) organized two significant Demo Farm Events on 11 May and 14 June 2023. These events occurred at two vineyards located just outside Zevgolateio and another in the broader Nemea region.</p> <p>The Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) team played a central role in these events. They led the efforts in establishing and meticulously monitoring a field trial designed to evaluate the effectiveness of cover crop monocultures and mixtures, along with the application of natural herbicides like hot foam and pelargonic acid. These natural herbicides were explored as promising alternatives to chemical methods for weed management. The field trial played a crucial role in offering practical insights into sustainable farming practices. Furthermore, one of the Demo Farm Events incorporated modern agricultural technology. It featured the deployment of an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) for spraying, conducted above the crop canopy. These UAV flights served as an educational tool, aiding stakeholders, students, and researchers in becoming acquainted with the principles and techniques of precision agriculture (PA). The integration of UAVs demonstrated how technology can enhance agricultural practices.</p> <p>Among the notable participants in the Demo Farm Event was Demosthenes Chachalis, a distinguished researcher who holds the position of Research Director and heads the</p>

	Laboratory of Weed Science at the esteemed Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI). His involvement underscored the event's significance in drawing together expertise from various quarters to explore sustainable and innovative approaches to agriculture.
Literature review/ projects review for → Identification and collection of alternative weed control methods and techniques	NNO and his team made their contribution to Oper8 Task 2.2 on a systematic basis. The Greek NNO identified the appropriate keywords to search for published data on the role of biological control, mowing, pre-harvest herbicides, seed rate, cultivar choice, and seeding pattern in weed management in arable and perennial crops. Led by NNO, the AUA team reviewed all the respecting scientific articles published in the literature on biological weed control, cultivar choice for weed suppression, preharvest weed control, mowing for weed control, seed rate manipulations for weed management, and seeding pattern manipulations for weed management, respectively. The findings from this extensive literature survey were documented in D2.1 and will undergo further analysis to produce a comprehensive review article on alternative non-chemical methods for weed control.
Cross visit events (26 April 2023)	The NNO participated and presented in the Oper8 webinar: Solutions for alternative weed control #1: Electric Weeding - Case studies in vineyard, grassland, and fruit production. The webinar was held on 26 April, 2023. The event was communicated beforehand to gather stakeholders interested on the topic. The NNO took part in the Oper8 kick-off meeting, which occurred on October 11, 2023. On the same day, a separate but related event was organized—a small demonstration event held at the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA)'s trial field. The purpose of this event was to familiarize participants with emerging technologies and non-chemical approaches for weed control. Notable among these methods were the application of hot foam and innovative weed suppression techniques involving energy crops, among others. This event aimed to showcase practical solutions for sustainable weed management.
Consortium Meeting Pisa	Ilias Travlos invited two experts for attending the meeting in Pisa.

3.1.3 France

NNOs Activity – Oper8 Year 1 in France	
Lugo NNOs Training Session	Camille Guilbert is the NNO for the French National Network. She presented the main results of the OG on intra-row cover crops held in Occitanie, South of France, to other Oper8 members attending Lugo event. She also presented the French National Network specializing in viticulture, based on IFV expertise, and main crop in the OG. She explained the aim is to involve Chambers of Agriculture with technical and agroecology advisors, independent winegrowers and winegrowers' cooperative, Water Agency. The challenge would be also to work with other relevant stakeholders from industry and research.
Needs, Barriers and Gaps questionnaire	Camille Guilbert and Fanny Prezman both reviewed the draft questionnaire before final version. Camille Guilbert, together with Fanny Prezman and the IFV communication team (national and local scale), broadcasted the survey through complementary channels: Linked In, National Network members, ACTA institute, Facebook Group (post on Machinery and Viticulture 'Matériel et Viticulture' Facebook group), experts' panel and their own networks, IFV South-West network through e-mailing, e-mails to work network. IFV also helped broadcasting other countries' surveys through the Climed-Fruit project network, especially for Italy and Spain, as they were partner countries in both projects. 104 people responded to the French survey, reaching the expected number by the end of February 2023.
Focus Group Meeting (to validate questionnaire results)	Camille Guilbert had been previously discussing with several National Network members about the upcoming focus group, and some of them expressed their interest to participate. An invitation e-mail was sent afterwards to gather the interested members and organize this meeting. The focus group meeting was held on 30 May, 2023. 10 people attended the focus group, including the two experts, plus

	<p>Camille Guilbert and Fanny Prezman who were organizing the meeting. Participants were from various target groups: policy maker, farmer, advisor, researcher, industry representative. Minutes and work documents were sent after the meeting.</p> <p>Camille Guilbert wrote the French part of the D2.1 report, with the survey results analysis, identification of needs and gaps, and with additional technical information coming from the focus group workshop.</p>
Demo Farm Events	<p>Two demo-farm events were organized during summer 2023. People were invited through various channels: Linked In event, Oper8 channels (website, social media), IFV networks, Facebook group.</p> <p>The first event was about dead mulch, it was held on 06 July. It was a presentation of dead mulch trials in a vineyard in Gard Region, South of France. 21 people plus Fanny Prezman and Camille Guilbert participated in this event, from farmers, to technical advisors, researchers, industry representatives. Various dead mulches were shown, with observation of weed density after three years of dead mulch use: organic matter felt mulch, oyster shells, vegetal waste, miscanthus straw, wood chips, bark. A wine-tasting was organized in the end, and most of the participants stayed for informal discussions.</p> <p>The second event was included in a big demo-farm day 'Vini Viti Vici' at IFV, V'Innopôle Sud-Ouest, on 20 July. A 'Zero-herbicide path' was gathering several demos, with dead mulch trials, mechanical weeding, robots, cover crops management tools, electrical weeding. Over 150 people attended the event, including many farmers, advisors, industry representatives, students.</p>
Literature review/ projects review for → Identification and collection of alternative weed control methods and techniques	<p>Fanny Prezman and Camille Guilbert were involved in the literature review. They worked on the different steps of the T2.2, from key works identification, first screening and second screening, mainly on dead mulch tactic for any crop, but also in the first steps, on water management. Camille Guilbert reviewed the whole D2.2.</p>
Cross visit events (26 April 2023)	<p>IFV is task leader for the T1.3, including webinar cross-visits. Camille Guilbert, Fanny Prezman, and IFV communication team worked on the webinar methodology, event organization and program. Camille Guilbert, as NNO, invited the French NN to attend the event. This event was also advertised in France through regular channels: IFV social media and networks (e-mailing, posts...) at local and national scale, repeated posts on Oper8 social media. 20 people from France registered, and 7 attended the event.</p>
Consortium Meeting Pisa	<p>The two experts Laure Gontier and Christophe Gaviglio were informed and invited in July to the demo-event (cross-visit) in Italian vineyards, planned for 24 October. Both expressed their real interest but cannot manage to be present in-person. Christophe Gaviglio confirmed his online participation.</p>

3.1.4 Italy

NNOs Activity – Oper8 Year 1 in Italy	
Lugo NNOs Training Session	<p>Lorenzo Tramacere presented outcomes from the trials carried out in the Italian OG, concerning the under-row cover cropping in vineyards. Afterwards, he introduced the NN challenges for Italy: scaling up from local-based OG to national level, wide range of crops and pedoclimatic conditions, involvement of policy makers</p>
Needs, Barriers and Gaps questionnaire	<p>Once the survey was translated Daniele Antichi and Lorenzo Tramacere shared it on the media platforms and also directly by emails to stakeholders who were just our contacts, asking them to share the survey as much as possible.</p> <p>Unfortunately, although we have re-shared the survey multiple times, we have obtained just 77 surveys completed.</p> <p>Daniele Antichi analysed the data.</p>
Focus Group Meeting (to validate questionnaire results)	<p>Lorenzo Tramacere and Daniele Antichi organized an online focus group meeting with 10 attendees, held online on 11 September 2023. Attendees included: three researchers (one with expertise in agricultural policy), one arable seed sealer, one regional government policy worker, one ministry policy worker, one vineyard</p>

	<p>agronomist and advisor, one arable agronomist and advisor, one agricultural machine sealer and one field vegetables expert</p> <p>The online meeting was hosted by Lorenzo Tramacere, Daniele Antichi, Christian Frasconi and Lorenzo Gagliardi.</p> <p>Lorenzo provided an overview of the project and the survey outcomes, and then towards an interactive sessionMentimeter (https://www.mentimeter.com) we have collected opinions about barriers and solutions to increase the spread of alternative weed control methods. In this way we were able to easily extract the results. Afterwards, we have led a discussion based on the outcomes of the serious game.</p>
Demo Farm Events	<p>Lorenzo Tramacere and Daniele Antichi organized two demo farm events in two vineyard farms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 08 June 2023, Castellani Farm (Peccioli, Pisa): the topic was the termination of the inter-row cover crop mixture using a roller crimper with the aim to let the cover crop on the ground as a dead mulch - 21 July 2023, Monterosola Farm (Volterra, Pisa): the topic was the management of the vineyard using a self-reseeding cover crop under the row <p>We had a low number (about 10) of attendees because in Italy the best time for the field demonstration overlapped with a very busy period for the farmers</p>
Literature review/ projects review for → Identification and collection of alternative weed control methods and techniques	<p>Lorenzo Tramacere was involved in the literature review (T2.2) and he helped to define some search keywords used for the Scopus searching. Moreover, he carried out the screening for the techniques “tillage and cultivation depth” and “seedbed preparation”</p>
Cross visit events (26 April 2023)	<p>The NNO helped circulate the invite to the 1st webinar event on 26 April 2023 and 12 people participated from Italy.</p> <p>The cross visit will be carried out during the annual meeting (23-24 October 2023), where we will visit some farms. This it will be a farm involved in our OG (Monterosola farm). We will have all the consortium of the Oper8 project that will attend at the annual meeting in Pisa. Moreover, Italian farmers, stakeholders and our National Experts will attend the cross visit, but at the moment we cannot provide an exact number.</p>
Consortium Meeting Pisa	<p>We will have a National Expert, Professor Camilla Moonen (School of advanced studies, Sant’Anna, Pisa). We have asked another NE (linked to the Agricultural Ministry), but their attendance is not yet confirmed.</p>

3.1.5 Sweden

NNOs Activity – Oper8 Year 1 in Sweden	
Lugo NNOs Training Session	<p>AGROVAST members were not able to attend the meeting physically, but Mats Emilson, CEO of Agroväst, presented a PowerPoint during the meeting describing our OG in which a tool for site-specific applications of herbicides in cereal crops was presented.</p> <p>Mats also presented our NN challenges: We have a broad, active AKIS-network and we are confident that Oper8 can align to this. We plan to arrange a number of events primarily dealing with using robotics and drones for scouting and to control weeds.</p>
Needs, Barriers and Gaps questionnaire	<p>AGROVAST faced substantial problems in reaching the target of 100 answers on the questionnaire: Only 51 answers were collected although it was very widely distributed through a variety of channels, both social media, by sending e-mails to selected persons and even to make phone calls.</p> <p>The reasons are probably two-fold:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The questionnaire was a little long and demanding and to some extent it was a challenge to translate in an unambiguous way.

	<p>2. People get a huge amount of questionnaires today and this has as we judge it, increased a lot only during the last few years. Our impression is that questionnaires need to be planned in detail both in terms of content, who to address and when to contact the potential respondents.</p>
Focus Group Meeting (to validate questionnaire results)	<p>On the other hand, this meeting went smoothly and we had enough participants (13). The meeting was held on-line and all participants had been contacted about 10 days in advance by phone. When contacted on the phone, they were also asked when it would be suitable for them to attend a meeting. The main take-home messages from the meeting were that it is very important to improve the agricultural concepts such as crop rotations, the use of catch-crops and to encourage the use of perennial crops. The participants were convinced that economic benefits, such as subsidies for investing in technical solutions such as robots, are needed to achieve a large-scale transition.</p>
Demo Farm Events	<p>In Sweden, we have so far taken part in the arrangement of two DEMO- activities. One was held on the 13 April 2023, Drone Day, in which we presented the Oper8 project, and the company Spraydrone demonstrated their solutions using drones to spray glyphosate site-specifically. This event had 80 attendants.</p> <p>The other event was held on the 31 August and this event was called the Hortic and Potatoes Day. Here a selection of different techniques to control weeds in horticultural crops were demonstrated, from cover crops in strawberries and red beets to a demonstration of the Norwegian Kilter robot that can save 95% of the herbicides by only spraying weeds. The event had about 500 participants. We have advertised the events both through Oper8 website and at the Agroväst website.</p>
Literature review/ projects review for → Identification and collection of alternative weed control methods and techniques	<p>Thomas Börjesson has gone through the DSS-articles and selected the ones that are relevant for the project.</p>
Cross visit events (26 April 2023)	<p>NNO in Sweden and the AGROVAST team have taken part in the distribution of invitations to this event and 10 participants from Sweden took part.</p>
Consortium Meeting Pisa	<p>Thomas Börjesson and Charlotte Wångdahl will take part. One national expert has also been invited for the demo-event on the 24 October.</p>

3.1.6 Latvia

NNOs Activity – Oper8 Year 1 in Latvia	
Lugo NNOs Training Session	<p>A presentation about Latvia's NN was prepared focusing on the aim of the NN, main actors, activity plan, and communication channels. Similarly, another presentation was prepared about our OG including information about the OG overview, OG's previous progress, and plans within the OPER8 project.</p>
Needs, Barriers and Gaps questionnaire	<p>In order to get the responses, the different target group reaching methods were used – provided information into the ZSA weekly news, individual emails were sent, also in WhatsApp groups contacted, phone calls made.</p> <p>In Latvian survey we reached in total 111 respondents: 91 farmers, and 20 non-farmers.</p>
Focus Group Meeting (to validate questionnaire results)	<p>E-mails and some individual phone calls were made to the focus group- representing different areas- advisors/consultants, researchers, farmers, governmental representatives, plant protection product representatives.</p> <p>We carried out the online interviews and afterwards the report was written, taking into the account the opinions of the focus group.</p>
Demo Farm Events	<p>The information about the demo event and invitation to attend the DEMO event was published online: Facebook, ZSA (FP) and Agrihorts web pages. At the event, we demonstrated the laser weeding robot in practice and popularised the project and alternative weed control methods (prepared materials by project partners). We also prepared a small survey for farmers and non-farmers to prove the number of</p>

	attendants at the DEMO event and to find out the attitude of visitors towards different weeding issues in agriculture. Totally we collected 70 answers on small survey, but many more people visited our site without filling out a survey.
Literature review/ projects review for → Identification and collection of alternative weed control methods and techniques	Agrihorts participated in the following literature screening stages: i) in identification of keywords, our topics were: Hand weeding, weed seed collection & destruction, and contributed Thermal weeding; ii) in the first screening stage we contributed the following topics: Sowing date; Liming; Sensing Technologies; Mowing.
Cross visit events (26 April 2023)	The information was sent to the farmers and stakeholders. And was put online on ZSA (FP)and LBTU webpages.
Consortium Meeting Pisa	The national expert Elīza Ilze Malceniece will attend the meeting on 24 October, 2023. She also representing the one of the demo farms “Bracas”. Representatives from ZSA (FP) and LBTU will also attend these meeting.

3.1.7 The UK

NNOs Activity – Oper8 Year 1 in the UK	
Lugo NNOs Training Session	<p>Lynn Tatnell (NNO) presented findings on electrical weeding and contributed to discussions on NN challenges and how to overcome them.</p> <p>Kevin Godfrey (NNO) presented findings on camera guided mechanical weeding.</p>
Needs, Barriers and Gaps questionnaire	<p>ADAS had a major role in writing the survey along with Latvia, liaising with all partners to get it translated, editing the final version and delivering it in the online software format.</p> <p>The ADAS team helped promote the UK survey via a range of different media platforms and the UK received 111 completed surveys.</p> <p>Eleanor Dearlove analysed the UK data and provided a template for all other partners to follow to simplify the data analysis. She then collated the data from all countries to contribute the D2.1.</p>
Focus Group Meeting (to validate questionnaire results)	<p>Kevin actively invited a wide range of experts from across the UK to become stakeholders in Oper8 and join the focus group meeting.</p> <p>ADAS organised an online focus group meeting with 13 attendees, held online on 13 July 2023. Attendees consisted of our two national experts, six researchers, one arable farmer, government policy workers, one horticulture agronomist, two Agriculture and Horticulture development board (AHDB) scientists and one technical officer (Linking Environment and Farming (LEAF)). Farmer attendance was low due to the busy time of year in the UK farming calendar.</p> <p>The workshop involved an overview of the project presented by Lynn and the details of the UK survey outcomes presented by Eleanor, and then a discussion on both the barriers to uptake of alternative weed control techniques and the solutions to overcome these. An online whiteboard was used to enable both verbal and written discussion and the barriers and solutions were grouped in to five main categories to provide structure for the meeting and the outcomes. Kevin, Lynn and Eleanor hosted the meeting and facilitated the discussion.</p> <p>ADAS produced a structured template of the focus group and survey outcomes for all partners to input their countries data and then produced the final report D2.2.</p>
Demo Farm Events	<p>Lynn Tatnell co-organised an EWRS (European Weed Research Society) workshop event where ADAS promoted and presented the Oper8 project, survey results and demonstrated electrical weeding and mechanical weeding (24-26 May 2023).</p> <p>ADAS attended a number of events in 2023 including:</p> <p>Three Rootwave electrical weeding demonstrations to promote Oper8 and present our research findings on electrical weeding (27 July, 9 & 16 August). Presentations by Lynn and Kevin.</p>

	<p>British leafy salad growers association – demo day (21 June). ADAS showcased mechanical weeders from Edwards farm machinery, promoted Oper8 (banner & flyers) and spoke with a number of alternative weed control manufacturers for possible collaboration later in the project.</p> <p>Lynn attended a Defra (UK government) IPM event and farm walk on a LEAF (Linking environment and farming) farm presenting Oper8 (14 June). ADAS and the Organic Research Centre (ORC) attended two Newcastle University open days (20 June & 05 July) to demonstrate the chameleon system (seeder and mechanical weeder) and to promote the wider Oper8 project (presentation/banner & flyers).</p> <p>Normac machinery demo day (06 Sept) – ADAS showcased inter row hoes from Kverneland and promoted Oper8 (banner & flyers).</p> <p>ADAS and ORC also attended a number of larger agricultural events to promote Oper8 (Groundswell 28-29 June, National Organic Conference 04 July) and presented our OGs at a range of farming meetings (ADAS Rosemaund Open day 20 June) and policy makers events.</p>
Literature review/ projects review for → Identification and collection of alternative weed control methods and techniques	Kevin Godfrey carried out the screening for the technique ‘sowing date’ as part of the literature review in T2.2
Cross visit events (26 April 2023)	<p>Lynn and Kevin both presented at the first Oper8 Webinar on electrical weed control. They shared experiences of electrical weeding trials in fruit and grassland cropping systems. They answered questions directed at their talks. ADAS invited an external speaker (Tom Archer from Rootwave).</p> <p>ADAS promoted the webinar event by sharing on social media and through the ADAS farming networks and wider UK. A total of 34 people attended from the UK and overall attendance was 124 people (~200 people registered in advance).</p>
Consortium Meeting Pisa	ADAS invited Dr Sarah Cook and James Clarke (UK Experts) to the consortium meeting in Pisa. James Clarke was unavailable, but Sarah Cook has agreed to attend. Sarah is a Principal research scientist in weed biology at ADAS with over 35 years’ experience in weed control and agronomy.

3.1.8 Lessons learnt and problematics faced

In the first year of the EU H2020 project Oper8, the eight (8) NNOs from the seven (7) NNs were involved in various activities aimed at advancing the project’s goals related to alternative weed control methods in agriculture. Here are some key lessons learnt and problematics faced based on the activities of these NNOs:

a) Lessons Learnt:

- **Effective Communication and Collaboration:** The success of survey distribution and focus group meetings depended on effective communication and collaboration within NNO teams. Coordinated efforts, diverse outreach channels, and personal contacts helped reach the target audience.
- **Local Adaptation:** Each NNO tailored its approach to the local context, such as the type of farming, climate, and target audience. This localized approach yielded valuable insights and increased participation.
- **Importance of National Experts:** National experts played a crucial role in focus group meetings and providing in-depth insights. Their involvement enhanced the quality of discussions and analysis.

- Data Analysis and Reporting: Standardized templates and data analysis methods facilitated the compilation of survey results and focus group outcomes into comprehensive reports for the project.

b) Problematics Faced:

- Survey Response Rate: Some NNOs faced challenges in achieving the desired survey response rate. Factors such as survey length, complexity, and survey fatigue among potential respondents impacted participation.
- Timing Issues: Timing was a significant challenge, as some demo farm events coincided with busy periods in the farming calendar. This affected attendance and limited farmer participation.
- Language Barriers: The need for translation and clarity in survey questions posed difficulties in some NNs. Ensuring that surveys are accessible and easy to understand is crucial.
- Varied Farmer Engagement: Engaging farmers in focus group meetings proved challenging due to their busy schedules and varying levels of interest in research activities.
- Cross-Network Coordination: Coordinating activities across multiple NNOs and NNs required meticulous planning and communication. Differences in regulations, farming practices, and language added complexity.
- Survey Promotion: Promoting surveys effectively was essential, and not all NNOs achieved their target response rate. Strategies for reaching a broader audience need continuous improvement.
- Balancing Research and Outreach: NNOs had to strike a balance between conducting research and engaging in outreach activities. The workload for both activities was substantial.
- Data Collection Challenges: Gathering relevant literature and data for the literature review posed challenges, particularly in accessing and screening scientific articles.

Overall, the first year of the Oper8 project demonstrated the importance of adaptability, effective communication, and the need for continuous improvement in survey design and outreach strategies. Despite challenges, the project made significant progress in understanding alternative weed control methods and engaging stakeholders in the agricultural sector.

Part. 4 Conclusion

In summary, this report highlights the pivotal achievements within the Oper8 project regarding the establishment of National Networks (NNs) and the instrumental role played by National Network Operators (NNOs) during its first year of activities.

The formation of Oper8 National Networks, underpinned by the expertise and commitment of NNOs, represents a significant milestone in advancing sustainable weed control practices throughout Europe and the wider UK. These networks serve as catalysts for stakeholder engagement, fostering meaningful dialogues among a diverse array of target groups. Anchored by a set of guiding principles encompassing flexibility, co-construction, multi-level interactions, impartiality, and transparency, these NNs have laid a solid foundation for Oper8's mission.

The strategic selection and training of NNOs have been paramount in driving the project's vision. In the Physical Training Session held in Lugo, NNOs have been equipped with essential skills, enabling them to proficiently prepare surveys, facilitate workshops, and craft comprehensive reports. Their proactive adoption of engaging and participatory tools, as for example by the use of Microsoft Forms for surveys, promises to enhance knowledge transfer and streamline workshop preparations.

Key activities undertaken by NNOs in alignment with Oper8's primary goals included

- **Needs, Barriers, and Gaps Questionnaire:** NNOs spearheaded the distribution of an online survey under Task 2.1 to gauge the readiness of farmers to embrace alternative weed control methods and identify potential obstacles. This extensive outreach effort reached a diverse network of contacts, both within and outside the National Networks (NNs), facilitating robust data collection.
- **Focus Group Meetings:** Subsequent to the survey, NNOs organized focus group workshops within each country. These gatherings aimed to bring together a minimum of 10 participants, representing a spectrum of stakeholders involved in weed management, including farmers, advisors, and policymakers. These sessions were instrumental in analysing survey results, gaining deeper insights into the prevailing context, and pinpointing unique needs and challenges within different cropping systems.
- **Demo Farm Events:** NNOs successfully coordinated several Demo Farm events, with the goal of hosting at least two per year per Operational Group (OG) and involving a minimum of 60-70 participants per country. These events provided hands-on exposure to alternative weed control methods.
- **Cross-Visit Events:** Online cross-visits, themed as 'Webinars on Alternative Weed Control,' are expected to be organized biannually. These sessions featured presentations on specific solutions and encouraged cross-fertilization of ideas among experts and stakeholders. With over 115 participants in each webinar, these events served as valuable knowledge-sharing platforms.
- **Literature Review/Projects Review:** Most NNOs actively participated in Task 2.2, contributing to the literature review of available alternative weed control methods. This involved identifying, collecting, and reviewing scientific and technical solutions from EU-funded and national projects, as well as EIP-AGRI focus group publications.

Also, NNOs provided support to other events such as the Consortium meeting to be held in October 2023 by providing experts that will participate in the expert panel. A summary of each NNO activity can be found in this report referring to figures achieved but also challenges and problematics faced.

In summary, NNOs have demonstrated unwavering dedication and resourcefulness in driving Oper8's mission forward during its inaugural year. The NNOs efforts have played a key role in boosting collaboration, sharing insights, and paving the way for the practical application of alternative weed control strategies. As we look to the second year of the project, the NNOs remain integral to the project's success, poised to further advance the cause of sustainable weed management practices across Europe. In conclusion, Oper8's inaugural year has witnessed the emergence of a robust network, driven by the dedication and competence of NNOs.

OPER 8

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

USC | María Rosa Mosquera Losada
Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro

NNOs Training – How to prepare an online survey

01 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

How to prepare an online survey

OPER 8

- Introduction
- Platforms
- Agenda
- Stakeholder participation (categories)
- Results
- Discussion and
- Annexes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

How to prepare an online survey

- Introduction
- Platforms
- Practice session

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Introduction

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

How to prepare an online survey

- Introduction
- **Platforms**
- Practice session

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Platforms

Microsoft Forms

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Platforms

Google Forms

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

How to prepare an online survey

- Introduction
- Preparatory Activities
- **Practice session**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Practice session

OPER 8

Preparatory Survey(s)

OPER 8

In order to organize the meeting and preparing logistics, NNOs must create and circulate an online survey in order to get stakeholders registration:

- 1.- Contact details (name and surname, e-mail, phone number, post-code, gender, age, organization, position in your organization)
- 2.- Please briefly describe the most relevant elements of your professional experience in relation to identifying and addressing the needs of forest-dominant rural areas, as well as whether you have experience using the CAP to address them.
3. What are your main reasons and motivations for applying to take part in this National Network?
4. If possible, please briefly describe how your organisation's experience working with forest-dominant rural areas may be useful for other rural areas with similar needs and issues.
5. Are you already networking with other stakeholders or Member States / regions on these issues? If so, please describe.
6. What, in your opinion, are the top three needs or issues facing weeding in rural areas?
7. Do you have any good examples of how the CAP has been used to support the needs of forest-dominant rural areas? If so, please briefly provide an example / case study / good practice example.
8. Would you be willing to present good practice example(s) to the TG?
9. Stakeholder category
10. Information on logistics such as lunch organization (attending? vegan option?), activities within the workshop as field trip (need of transportation).
11. Interactions with other projects (H2020, LIFE...)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Practice session

OPER 8

National Workshops assessment

OPER 8

In order to Checking the meeting quality, a survey must be sent with regard to:

- Preparatory activities
- Meeting Place
- Documents provided
- Food
- Timing
- Field trip
- Agenda distribution
- Networking

All these items could be assessed by **rating from 1 to 5**, it should be included a **final open question in order to ask for suggestions and potential improvements**.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

Thank you!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

USC | María Rosa Mosquera Losada
Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro

NNOs Training – Preparatory Activities

01 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

National Network Operators training

OPER 8

- Introduction
- Preparatory activities
 - Stakeholders selection
 - Content presentation
 - Creating an Agenda
 - Invitation Letter
 - Information Sheet
 - Research consent form and expression of commitment
 - Registration and Networking evaluation Survey(s)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

National Network Operators training

OPER 8

- **Introduction**
- Preparatory activities
 - Stakeholders selection
 - Content presentation
 - Creating an Agenda
 - Invitation Letter
 - Information Sheet
 - Research consent form and expression of commitment
 - Registration and Networking evaluation Survey(s)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

TASK 1.2 AIMS

OPER 8

Task 1.2 - Training and monitoring the NNOs [Lead: USC; Contributors: ALL; M04-M36]

This task will **train the 8 NNOs based on the guidelines specified in T1.1**. A dedicated physical training session will take place in M04 to

- * **introduce the stakeholder engagement**
- * **involvement tools and stimulate discussions on the NNOs' role.**

Three (3) virtual progress monitoring meetings will be held (M15, M27, and M35) for the NNOs to share insights and provide feedback on their work following the guidelines established in T1.1.

Focussed on:

- (i) **the exchange of experiences (e.g., success stories and difficulties);**
- (ii) **reviewing the approaches used; and**
- (iii) **adjusting and fine tuning the framework**

Additional exchanges of experiences among NNOs will be arranged as needed in the form of online meetings and at consortium meetings.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

Deliverables

- D1.2 Oper8 NNs, including **NNOs activities (version 1). Month 12**
- D1.4 Oper8 NNs, including **NNOs activities, improvements and updates (version 2). Month 24**
- D1.6 Oper8 NNs, including **NNOs activities, improvements and updates (version 3) Month 35**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

What is a NN in Oper8

Based on the Oper8 objectives, NNs are...

- Tool through to collect stakeholders knowledge and opinions in each country.
- Forums for the two-way exchanges of ideas for co-learning and co-creation of knowledge with actors at European and national levels
- A mix of actors from various target groups (farmers, advisors, agri-food industry, research community, policymakers, citizens, and consumers) in debates about alternative weed control.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Workshops within Oper8

Workshop 1 →

Task 3.1 – National Workshop on National Action Plans [**Lead: IFV**, Contributors: All partners; M13-M15]
 This Task will involve an initial **evaluation** of the **surveys reported in the National Action Plans (D3.1)** inventoried solutions by organising a first round of National Workshops (M13-M14) in each NN. The evaluation will be based **on criteria co-established by the National Experts and the workshop participants** (i.e. solutions already applied in practice, easy of use). This first round of evaluation **will output the solutions to be analysed in terms of costs and benefits** (T3.2).

Workshop 2 →

Task 3.3 – National Workshop on Readiness & Acceptability [**Lead: UNIPI**, Contributors: IFV; M15-M23]
 Further **evaluation of the readiness** and acceptability of the cost/benefit analysed solutions based on four criteria:

- (i) **technical readiness** (can it be applied on farms in the short-term?)
- (ii) **ease of implementation** within different farming systems considered in the project
- (iii) **need for training and education**
- (iv) **need for investment**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

First: Selection of solutions (12 per country) in month 13-15 from the national action plans (survey Task 2.4) in the task 3.1 to be analysed through a cost/Benefit analysis in the task 3.2

Second: Adoptability analysis in task 3.3 in month 21 to 22 of those solutions that had already the cost/Benefit analysis done in task 3.2

Technical readiness

Easiness of implementation

Need of training and education

Need of investment

A total number of **80 Best Practices will be generated (about 12 per NN)**, which will be translated and adapted as Best Practices in WP4.

The outcomes of both tasks will also **update the Oper8 Digital Inventory (T2.3)**.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Principles for setting-up NN in Oper8

First guiding principle: flexible and adaptable programming

Adopt an approach of flexible content and timing programming to allow timely contributions from Oper-8 NNs in line with the EU policies adapting functioning NNs to new needs and challenges as they arise.

Second guiding principle: co-construction

Maintain discussion and dialogue with representatives of the target groups. Members of the NNs should be able to express themselves freely and should be treated equally. Aspects like gender, age should be considered, among others

Third guiding principle: multi-level interactions

Ensuring fruitful interaction among actors at multiple levels of governance (from local to the EU), within local, regional and national policymaking, to the European 'landscape', and to the global context to support the development of policies at the EU level and formulate recommendations for future EU research agendas and agricultural policies dealing with weeding.

Fourth guiding principle: impartiality and transparency

1. Multiple contributions and peer review of each public document produced, that will be peer-reviewed by multiple consortium actors and relevant information validated by networks.
2. Documentation: the outcomes of consultations and discussions should be documented and available for scrutiny by members of the NNs and members of the consortium.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Plan meetings: the Three P Statements

OPER 8

Purpose states what you plan to accomplish. Stating this intention or purpose answers some fundamental questions. Why are we here? What is the goal? Why this meeting is necessary?

Workshop 1. **Evaluation of the surveys reported in the National Action Plans (M12-15)**

Workshop 2. **National Workshop on Readiness & Acceptability (M21-22)**

Process describes how the meeting will address the topic under consideration and answers additional important questions. How will we proceed? What techniques will we use? What steps will we take? How long will this last? What is expected of me? What is expected of the group?

Product informs the participants of the benefit/product, or what they will get from the discussion, and resolves the following questions. Why bother? What is in it for me to participate? What are the real benefits? How will this affect our group's goals?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

NETWORKING ACTIVITIES

- **Preparatory activities**
- **Workshop Development**
- **Reporting**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

- Introduction
- **Preparatory activities**
 - **Stakeholders selection**
 - Content presentation
 - Creating an Agenda
 - Invitation Letter
 - Information Sheet
 - Research consent form and expression of commitment
 - Registration and Networking evaluation Survey(s)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Stakeholders selection

A set of stakeholders will be carefully selected for the meetings, including at least **30% of farmers as compulsory but also include**

- Farmers
- Advisors
- Agri-food industry
- Research community
- Policymakers,
- Citizens and consumers
- EIP-AGRI and CAP networks

Cross fertilisation activities	Total	Minimum requirement	Desirable	Outstanding
National & European Workshops	-at least 120 actors involved in evaluation of the solutions - 80 solutions for cost benefit analysis	- 40 stakeholders per country -at least 15 stakeholders per OG for evaluation of the solutions - 80 solutions for cost benefit analysis	- 45 stakeholders per country -at least 20 stakeholders per OG for evaluation of the solutions - 85 solutions for cost benefit analysis	- 50 stakeholders per country -at least 25 stakeholders per OG for evaluation of the solutions - 90 solutions for cost benefit analysis

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Stakeholders selection

The NNOs are tasked with identifying and inviting the most suitable organisations or individuals to participate in each NN, based on their national and regional expertise.

Criteria	Explanation
Interest and Willingness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actors should demonstrate an interest in the co-creation of knowledge for alternative weed control. Actors will be selected for their willingness to share their own knowledge and to listen to others.
Criteria	Explanation
Availability/Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actors will be asked if they can make a commitment to being part of a NN to be continuing as part of NN over the course of the project, enhancing members getting known each other, build mutual trust, and become more comfortable in participating in a spirit of openness.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Stakeholders selection

Criteria	Explanation
Balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The composition of membership of the NNs as a whole should ensure stakeholders, views, approaches, balance.
Criteria	Explanation
Representativeness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invitations to actors will specify whether they are representing an organisation or attending as individuals.
Criteria	Explanation
Gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efforts will be made to ensure gender balance in the membership of NNs.
Criteria	Explanation
Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efforts will be made to ensure a range of ages for members in NNs
Criteria	Explanation
Actor Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AKIS actors: advisors, farmers and foresters, cooperatives, rural CAP networks, OGs Policy (e.g., elected politician or official working at public authority at local, regional or national level). Scientific actors such as universities or research institutes produce new knowledge on a range of issues which are important for the development of rural areas. Industry (smart farming technologies)

- Introduction
- **Preparatory activities**
 - Stakeholders selection
 - **Content presentation**
 - Creating an Agenda
 - Invitation Letter
 - Information Sheet
 - Research consent form and expression of commitment
 - Registration and Networking evaluation Survey(s)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Presenting the National Action Plans survey results

- Present country results but considering the other country results, mostly related to the same crops and biogeographic conditions
- When are the results from the survey available? This is needed to organize the content of the workshop and should be available in advance to prepare the workshop
- How to make a good presentation?
 - The simpler, the better →
 - Try placing important points in bullet points.
 - Figures or tables better than text
 - Create an structure as if you were part of the audience →
 - Ask yourself what is the best order
 - Give a narrative to your presentation
 - Use visual aids →
 - Incorporate photos or videos
 - Design →
 - Do not use blocks of text
 - Use a minimalistic background
 - Maintain a consistent font style and size
 - 10-20-30 rule →
 - 10 slides, 20 minutes & font size 30

1/31/23

- Introduction
- **Preparatory activities**
 - Stakeholders selection
 - Content presentation
 - **Creating an Agenda**
 - Invitation Letter
 - Information Sheet
 - Research consent form and expression of commitment
 - Registration and Networking evaluation Survey(s)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Creating an Agenda

Creating an effective agenda is one of the most important elements for a productive meeting. The main steps to follow are:

- Give the agenda a title
- Include "who?", "where?", and "when?" information in the header
- Add an e-mail, phone number and contact point
- Send and link to an on-line form for registration
- Write a brief statement of the meeting objective(s)
- Write a schedule outlining the main elements of the meeting
- Check the agenda for errors before distributing it
- Leave extra time for discussion at the end of each section and of the meeting for Q&A
- Develop a similar agenda to all National Networks considering specificities (section running workshops) for each national network
- Send the invitation letter, the explanation of Oper8 and the Agenda at least one month advance
- Send reminders 15, 7 and 1 day before the meetings
- Make a field trip linked to farmers practicing sustainable weeding practices linked to the operational group

Agenda	
9:00-9:20	Welcome & Introduction
9:20-11:00	XXX
Coffee Break	
11:30-12:00	XXX
12:00-13:50	XXX
Lunch Break	
15:00-15:40	XXX
15:40-16:30	XXX
17:00-17:40	XXX
17:40-18:00	XXX

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

- Introduction
- **Preparatory activities**
 - Stakeholders selection
 - Content presentation
 - Creating an Agenda
 - **Invitation Letter**
 - Information Sheet
 - Research consent form and expression of commitment
 - Registration and Networking evaluation Survey(s)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Invitation Letter

A draft of the Invitation letter has been included in D1.1

Oper8 Invitation Letter

Dear **NNO**, please translate to local language (if you find it necessary) and insert the following letter into an e-mail to invite stakeholders to your National Network. **Please also attach the information sheet to the e-mail.**

Invitation to join a National Network of the Oper8 project.

Dear **TITLE AND NAME**,

The Oper8 Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups (OGs) on alternative weed control, invites you to become a member of the Oper8 thematic network in **INSERT NAME OF REGION AND/OR STATE** National Network (NN). By following both a bottom up and a top-down approach, the AIS systems developed around the selected eight (8) OGs will be expanded to seven (7) National Networks. The Oper8 NNs are environments, where actors from the sphere of alternative weed control management meet, share and co-create knowledge on non-chemical solutions. As a member of a NN you come from one of these groups:

1. Farmers / Cooperatives
2. Advisors / Consulting companies
3. Agri-food industry
4. Research community
5. Policymakers
6. Citizens / Consumers
7. IIP-AGRI and CAP networks

The interaction between these target groups will take place in seven (7) countries. The NNs will formulate recommendations, aiming to influence European research agenda for alternative weed control. The activity in each NN is supported by the selected NNO and the encounters will be carried out in local language.

The Oper8 project is a research project funded by the EU via Horizon Europe. The project is carried out by a consortium of ten (10) partner organisations coordinated by the Agricultural University of Athens in Greece, and contracted by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement 101060591.

What is in it for you?

The Oper8 NNs are created to reflect different regional stakeholder perspectives and interests on innovative Operational Group weed control solutions, and to communicate these to ongoing policy processes at EU-level. As member of the NN, you have an opportunity to join other actors from the spheres of alternative weed control to discuss important matters and raise main points to the EU.

We would value your perspective and contribution as a member of one of the 7 national NNs. As a minimum, this means to participate in Oper8 activities, and possibly also in meetings during at least six (6) months of the Oper8 project. Please see the attached information sheet for more details.

You are cordially invited (upon your acceptance of this invitation), to become a member in the NN in **INSERT REGION**. To confirm your willingness and availability to join the national NN, please send me your answer by the end of **INSERT DATE MONTH AND YEAR**. Members of the NNs will also be asked to sign a Research Consent Form and Expression of Commitment to formalize participation.

Please do not hesitate to get back to me for any questions.

I look forward to hearing from you.

Yours sincerely,

NNO for the regional NN in INSERT COUNTRY NAME, NAME, AFFILIATION, EMAIL ADDRESS, TELEPHONE NUMBER

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060591

25 | P a g e

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

- Introduction
- Preparatory activities
 - Stakeholders selection
 - Content presentation
 - Creating an Agenda
 - Invitation Letter
 - Information Sheet
 - Research consent form and expression of commitment
 - Registration and Networking evaluation Survey(s)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Information Sheet

A draft of the Information Sheet has been included in D1.1

Part 7 Annex 2

Oper8 National Network Information Sheet

What is Oper8?

The European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control (Oper8 project), engages members from the spheres of alternative weed control in formulating recommendations with the ambition to influence European research agenda for weed management. Oper8 will set-up a self-sustainable, multi-actor, EU-wide Thematic Network to support and promote solutions for non-chemical weed control by building upon the knowledge and outcomes of eight (8) Operational Groups and stimulate knowledge exchange among all relevant actors and stakeholders. The interaction between involved target groups will take place in a total of seven (7) National Networks (NNs) placed in seven (7) countries.

Through the work and the knowledge and outcomes of eight (8) Operational Groups (OGs), Oper8 will maximize their potential, by broadening them into National Networks within the AKIS ecosystem. For the succession of this goal, the role and contribution of the National Network Operators is necessary, as they will bring together and stimulate cooperation among the partner OGs and the AKIS actors.

The Oper8 project is a three-year research project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, contracted by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement 101060591. It is carried out by a consortium of ten (10) partner organisations in the EU and is coordinated by the Agricultural University of Athens, based in Greece.

What is a National Network (NN)?

The Oper8 NNs are nationally based environments. Their goal will be to maximize the potential of the already existing Operational Groups (OGs), in the NNs, actors from the spheres of alternative weed control will meet, share and co-create knowledge on the required topics.

As a member of a NN you come from one of these groups:

1. Farmers / Cooperatives
2. Advisors / Consulting companies
3. Agri-food industry
4. Research community
5. Policymakers
6. Citizens / Consumers
7. EIP-AGRI and CAP networks

Each NN has one person that is designated NNO, National Network Operator. This person is part of the project consortium and has the task of facilitating interaction in the NN. The NNO will be your contact person to the Oper8 project.

What will the NNs do?

The Oper8 project will (i) establish stakeholder engagement processes to assemble the NNs; (ii) capture the drivers, barriers, and root causes of lack of non-chemical weed control adoption as part of a bottom-up approach; (iii) establish cross-fertilisation activities within and between the NNs to co-create, showcase, and evaluate non-chemical weed control methods; and (iv) deploy knowledge transfer tools and techniques (workshops, demo farms, CAP Measures) to adapt and scale up alternative weed control solutions and ensure their diffusion within countries and across Europe produce various outcomes, that are relevant for sustainable weed control. The produced Policy Recommendations will be included in ongoing policy processes concerning European development policies and research agenda.

What are you being asked to do?

As a member of one NN, we would value your perspective and contribution on alternative weed control. As a member we expect you to participate in a variety of cross fertilisation activities (online/physical meetings, demo events, cross visits, training sessions, National/European workshops, Survey workshops) across the duration of the Oper8 project.

We would like you to sign a consent form and to participate in

- At least 1 cross-fertilisation activity.
- a minimum of 1 interaction per 6 months in your region or country to discuss relevant topics of alternative weed control.

Other activities that are relevant are for instance to contribute to social media communications on the topics discussed in your NN.

How long will the activity last and where will it take place?

Specific details about activity length, focus and location would be provided from the NNO at the time of invitation to take part in a meeting or a research activity.

How will the information be used?

Information will be used for project purposes only. It will be aggregated together with other information collected through other activities which focus on the Oper8 project objectives. Project findings will be published in the form of reports to the European Commission, on topics discussed, articles in scientific journals, papers and presentations at technical or scientific events, and to project partner teams participating in Oper8.

Additionally, Oper8 will disseminate research results to actors that the NNO finds relevant in their country or region.

Pseudonymity and confidentiality

We will ask for your name and contact details, which we will only use for our own project records, and so that we can contact you to share project outputs if you so wish. At any time, you have the right to ask for your contact details to be deleted from our records.

The information you give us will be treated as confidential and will be pseudonymized so that it cannot be linked to you personally. We will not disclose any details that could be used to identify you. If quotes are used in any output these will be pseudonymized, unless else is agreed with the NNO of my NN.

No obligation to take part.

Taking part in this study is entirely voluntary and you can withdraw at any time. During any activity you are free not to answer questions without any explanation. You will be asked to provide consent prior to joining the NN to show that you understand your rights as a participant and that you are committed to take part in the NN. This consent form will be sent to you by your NNO if you accept to participate.

Reimbursement of eligible costs incurred.

For some of the activities in the NN eligible costs for travel and accommodation to participate in a meeting can be reimbursed. Further details on this will be provided from the NNO of your NN.

Liability

The Oper8 project and project partners accept no liability for stakeholders participating in the research activity.

For more information please contact:

Project coordinator of Oper8: Spyros Fountas, Agricultural University of Athens, sfountas@aua.gr

Project manager of Oper8: Nicoleta Darra, Agricultural University of Athens, nicoletadarra@aua.gr

[NNO: INSERT NAME, address and email address of NNO.]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

- Introduction
- **Preparatory activities**
 - Stakeholders selection
 - Content presentation
 - Creating an Agenda
 - Invitation Letter
 - Information Sheet
 - **Research consent form and expression of commitment**
 - Registration and Networking evaluation Survey(s)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Research consent form and expression of commitment

A draft has been included in D1.1

Research consent form and expression of commitment

For individual participants in the National Networks (NNO) in the Oper8 project - European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and coordinated by AUA.

	Please tick box
I confirm that I have read, or had read to me, and understood the information sheet for the above study (see below). I have had the opportunity to ask questions, and these have been answered fully and explicitly.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I am free to withdraw at any time, without providing any reason and without my legal rights being affected.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that the project is carried out by a consortium of 10 partner organisations coordinated by AUA, and contracted by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement 101060591.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Unless other is agreed with the National Network Operator (NNO) of my NN, data will be pseudonymised at the earliest possible time and it will not be possible to identify who said what in any publication/output.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that this form relates to all the activities to which I am contributing within the Oper8 project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree to take part in the Oper8 project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree to being committed to a NN for a minimum period of 6 months.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree to being contacted by project partners in relation to this study after my participation in a NN has ended.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree for the information I provide to be recorded (e.g. audio, flipchart notes) and transcribed.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree that photos taken during Oper8-related activities can be shared on social media.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of Participant _____ Signature _____ Date _____

NNO Name _____ Signature _____ Date _____

28 | Page

[Add name of organisation of NNO] will use your personal data for the purposes of the research undertaken in the Oper8 project. Our legal basis for processing your data is that it is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest in relation to research funded by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement 101060591.

We are the Data Controller over your personal data. We will not share your personal data beyond the project team, unless required by law and shall only retain it according to good scientific practice for as long as is necessary to fulfil the research undertaken on the project, to deliver project outcomes, and to fulfil the requirements of the funder. Please see our Privacy Notice at [web address of organisation] for further information or contact our Data Protection Officer on [add email address of data protection officer].

[Insert NNO Name]

Contact details:

[Name of organisation]

[Address]

If there is no privacy notice on the partner's website, and if a partner does not have a Data Protection Officer, substitute the sentence with the following: "For further information please contact [add email address of person responsible for data protection]".

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

- Introduction
- **Preparatory activities**
 - Stakeholders selection
 - Content presentation
 - Creating an Agenda
 - Invitation Letter
 - Information Sheet
 - Research consent form and expression of commitment
 - **Registration and Networking evaluation Survey(s)**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Preparatory Survey(s)

In order to organize the meeting and preparing logistics, NNOs must create and circulate an online survey in order to get stakeholders registration:

- 1.- Contact details (name and surname, e-mail, phone number, post-code, gender, age, organization, position in your organization)
- 2.- Please briefly describe the most relevant elements of your professional experience in relation to identifying and addressing the needs of forest-dominant rural areas, as well as whether you have experience using the CAP to address them.
3. What are your main reasons and motivations for applying to take part in this National Network?
4. If possible, please briefly describe how your organisation's experience working with forest-dominant rural areas may be useful for other rural areas with similar needs and issues.
5. Are you already networking with other stakeholders or Member States / regions on these issues? If so, please describe.
6. What, in your opinion, are the top three needs or issues facing weeding in rural areas?
7. Do you have any good examples of how the CAP has been used to support the needs of forest-dominant rural areas? If so, please briefly provide an example / case study / good practice example.
8. Would you be willing to present good practice example(s) to the TG?
9. Stakeholder category
10. Information on logistics such as lunch organization (attending? vegan option?), activities within the workshop as field trip (need of transportation).
11. Interactions with other projects (H2020, LIFE...)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

Thank you!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

USC | María Rosa Mosquera Losada
Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro

NNOs Training – Reporting + Interactions

01 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Reporting Content

- Introduction
- Preparatory Activities
- Agenda
- Stakeholder participation (categories)
- Results
- Discussion and
- Annexes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Reporting Content

- **Introduction**
- Preparatory Activities
- Agenda
- Stakeholder participation (categories)
- Results
- Discussion and conclusions
- Annexes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Introduction

OPER 8

Make an introduction of your workshop, mentioning **all the previous work conducted** as:

- Documents sent in advance
- Summary of stakeholders composition
- Agenda
- Summary of the main results
 - 1st workshop: selection of 12 solutions coming from the National Action Plans
 - 2nd workshop: prioritization of the analysed solutions considering:
 - (i) **technical readiness** (can it be applied on farms in the short-term?)
 - (ii) **ease of implementation** within different farming systems considered in the project
 - (iii) **need for training and education**
 - (iv) **need for investment**
- Summary of the quality of networking (surveys)
- Networking Challenges Discussion
 - (i) **Networking success stories and difficulties**
 - (ii) **analysis of the approaches used**
 - (iii) **further improvements regarding the networking**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

Reporting Content

- Introduction
- **Preparatory Activities**
- Agenda
- Stakeholder participation (categories)
- Results
- Discussion and conclusions
- Annexes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Preparatory activities

A summary of the framework for this NN workshop including:

- The date and venue of the meeting
- The NNO name
- The responsible person of the institution hosting the NN
- The preparatory activities carried out for the organization of the workshop and meetings (including the process to set the final agenda)

Focus of this workshop based on the Oper8 NN objectives.

- 1st assessment of the National Action Plans and validation of the Oper8 inventory of solutions,
- 2nd check the readiness and acceptability of the selected ones

Explain the process for criteria of selection and the final selection and invitation of participants, including the sharing of the Agenda to the participants and registration form prior to the meeting.

Include information on surveys if sent, reminders or phone calls for engaging/inviting stakeholders to the workshop etc.

List the prepared information and material given to the stakeholders during the workshop (Agenda, info prepared on challenges or OG results etc.)

Procedures of intermeeting contact with stakeholders How? (Facebook, Newsletters...).Response from stakeholders

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Reporting Content

- Introduction
- Preparatory Activities
- **Agenda**
- Stakeholder participation (categories)
- Results
- Discussion and conclusions
- Annexes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Agenda

OPER 8

Agenda	
9:00-9:20	Welcome & Introduction
9:20-11:00	XXX
Coffee Break	
11:30-12:00	XXX
12:00-13:50	XXX
Lunch Break	
15:00-15:40	XXX
15:40-16:30	XXX
17:00-17:40	XXX
17:40-18:00	XXX

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

Reporting Content

- Introduction
- Preparatory Activities
- Agenda
- **Stakeholder participation (categories)**
- Results
- Discussion and conclusions
- Annexes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Stakeholder participation

Based on an excel that will be sent, fill the data as basement to describe the actors participation in your workshop, considering the categories included in the D1.1.

Make an overview of the participants with number, AKIS actor categories, institutions type and highlighting home institution if noticeable.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Reporting Content

- Introduction
- Preparatory Activities
- Agenda
- Stakeholder participation (categories)
- **Results**
- Discussion and conclusions
- Annexes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Results

Present the following results:

- * Pre-meeting survey results and the modification of the meeting
- * Content results
 - 1st workshop → Assessment of National Action Plans + validation of the Oper8 inventory of solutions a table, that will sent
 - 2nd workshop → Readiness and acceptability of the selected solutions with an scoring table
- * Networking results
 - Send the results of the networking quality check survey

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Reporting Content

- Introduction
- Preparatory Activities
- Agenda
- Stakeholder participation (categories)
- Results
- **Discussion and Conclusions**
- Annexes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Discussion

Discuss together the following items obtained from the results:

- * Pre-meeting survey results and the modification of the meeting
- * Content results
 - 1st workshop → Assessment of National Action Plans + validation of the Oper8 inventory of solutions a table, that will sent
 - 2nd workshop → Readiness and acceptability of the selected solutions with an scoring table
- * Networking results
 - Send the results of the networking quality check survey

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Reporting Content

- Introduction
- Preparatory Activities
- Agenda
- Stakeholder participation (categories)
- Results
- Discussion and Conclusions
- **Annexes**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Annexes

Include annexes including the next documents at least:

- Invitation letter/letter of commitment (included also in the D1.1)
- Agenda
- List of attendees
- Minutes of the meeting

Invitation to join a National Network of the Oper8 project.

Dear [TITLE AND NAME],

The Oper8 Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups (OGs) on alternative weed control, invites you to become a member of the Oper8 thematic network in [INSERT NAME OF REGION AND/OR STATE] National Network (NN).

By following both a bottom up and a top-down approach, the AKIS ecosystems developed around the selected eight (8) OGs will be expanded to seven (7) National Networks. The Oper8 NNs are environments, where actors from the sphere of alternative weed control management meet, share and co-create knowledge on non-chemical solutions. As a member of a NN you come from one of these groups:

1. Farmers / Cooperatives
2. Advisors / Consulting companies
3. Agri-food industry
4. Research community
5. Policymakers
6. Citizens / Consumers
7. EIP-AGRI and CAP networks

The interaction between these target groups will take place in seven (7) countries. The NNs will formulate recommendations, aiming to influence European research agenda for alternative weed control. The activity in each NN is supported by the selected NNO and the encounters will be carried out in local language.

The Oper8 project is a research project funded by the EU via Horizon Europe. The project is carried out by a consortium of ten (10) partner organisations coordinated by the Agricultural University of Athens in Greece, and contracted by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement 101060591.

What is in it for you?

The Oper8 NNs are created to reflect different regional stakeholder perspectives and interests on innovative Operational Group weed control solutions, and to communicate these to ongoing policy processes at EU level. As member of the NN, you have an opportunity to join other actors from the spheres of alternative weed control to discuss important matters and raise main points to the EU.

We would value your perspective and contribution as a member of one of the 7 national NNs. As a minimum, this means to participate in Oper8 activities, and possibly also in meetings during at least six (6) months of the Oper8 project. Please see the attached Information Sheet for more details.

You are cordially invited (upon your acceptance of this invitation), to become a member in the NN in [INSERT REGION]. To confirm your willingness and availability to join the national NN, please send me your answer by the end of [ADD DATE, MONTH AND YEAR]. Members of the NNs will also be asked to sign a Research Consent Form and Expression of **Commitment** to formalize participation.

Please do not hesitate to get back to me for any questions.
I look forward to hearing from you.
Yours sincerely,

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

www.oper-8.eu

OPER 8
Thank you!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

USC | María Rosa Mosquera Losada
Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro

NNOs Training – Running Workshops

01 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Content

OPER 8

- Tools for Meetings and Workshops
 - Group activities
 - Brainstorming
 - Gallery walk
 - Post-Up
 - Affinity Map
 - Individually
 - Voting techniques
- Agenda
- Documents
- NN interactions
- National Workshops assessment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Content

- **Tools for Meetings and Workshops**
 - Group activities
 - Brainstorming
 - Gallery walk
 - Post-Up
 - Affinity Map
 - Individually
 - Voting techniques
- Agenda
- Documents
- NN interactions
- National Workshops assessment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Tools for Meetings and Workshops

Brainstorming: it is a tool for generating ideas for a group of people around a specific area of interest. Using rules which remove inhibitions, people are able to think more freely and move into new areas of thought and so create numerous new ideas and solutions. All the ideas are noted down and are not criticized. Only when the brainstorming session is over the ideas are evaluated.

Rules of Brainstorming

- | | |
|--|--|
| One Conversation at a Time |
| Be Visual |
| Go for Quantity |
| Stay Focused on the Topic | |

© ISETO 2020

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Tools for Meetings and Workshops

Gallery walk: it is a discussion technique that gets people out of their chairs and actively involves them in synthesizing important concepts, in consensus building, in writing, and in public speaking

- The facilitator of the meeting prepares several discussion questions and groups people in teams.
- Questions are posted on different "stations" on room walls, placed on pieces of paper on desks in different locations around the room.
- At each posted question a team reviews what previous groups have written and adds new content.
- After a short period of time (three to five minutes), the facilitator asks for rotation. The group rotates to the next station. Rotation continues until all posted questions are addressed.
- When the group returns to the station where it started, the group synthesizes comments and makes an oral report to the room.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Tools for Meetings and Workshops

Post-Up: It is an innovation game aimed to generate ideas with silent sticky note writing.

- Facilitator writes the question or topic on a whiteboard.
- He asks the group to brainstorm answers individually, silently writing their ideas on separate sticky notes.
- After a set amount of time, facilitator asks the members of the group to stick their notes to the whiteboard and quickly present them.
- If anyone's items inspire others with new ideas add it into the wall too, after everyone has presented.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Tools for Meetings and Workshops

Affinity Map. This technique can be used when the facilitator wants to find categories and meta categories within a cluster of ideas and when he wants to see which ideas are most common within the group. This technique can be conducted only when the facilitator has a question for the players that he knows will generate at least 20 pieces of information to sort.

- On a sheet of flip-chart paper, he writes a question that the players will respond to along with a visual that complements it.
- He asks each player to take 10 minutes to generate sticky notes in response to the question (silently).
- The facilitator collects the ideas from the group and posts them on a flat working surface visible to everyone. Based on guidance from players, facilitator sorts the ideas into columns (or clusters) based on relationships. (Redundancy in ideas is OK)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Content

- Tools for Meetings and Workshops
 - Group activities
 - Brainstorming
 - Gallery walk
 - Post-Up
 - Affinity Map
 - Individually
 - Voting techniques
- Agenda
- Documents
- NN interactions
- National Workshops assessment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Voting techniques

Multi-Voting Math (or N/3): it is a technique used by small groups to quickly select a subset from a broader set of options. This democratic approach allows team member to cast a finite number of votes, with few restrictions (e.g., individuals can't "plump" all of their votes on one single candidate), for their options of choice.

The process yields a rank order. Some options, the ones with zero or few(er) votes are de-selected, so that the team's attention can be focused on the surviving options.

Multi-voting can be done iteratively to further reduce the options. $V = N/3$ Where:

V= the number of votes allocated to each team member (one to each option)

N= the number of options that are candidates to receive votes

Recall that ceiling brackets require rounding up to the nearest integer.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Voting techniques

Multiple Votes and Voting Rounds: it is a democracy system in which people are given multiple votes and the possible decisions with the highest scoring options go on to the next round in which fewer options are given. This group decision process is helpful in that participants are not restricted to one vote. Additionally, by using multiple rounds, participants can make decisions relative to options still available.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Content

- Tools for Meetings and Workshops
 - Group activities
 - Brainstorming
 - Gallery walk
 - Post-Up
 - Affinity Map
 - Individually
 - Voting techniques
- **Agenda**
- Documents
- NN interactions
- National Workshops assessment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

AGENDA

Based on the results of the survey, the meeting agenda will be prepared in order to proceed with similar methodology in all the NNs to obtain the expected results.

NNOs should agree on the main points of the agenda. Thus, NNOs should meet online to agree on it.

When we will have the results from the survey???

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Content

- Tools for Meetings and Workshops
 - Group activities
 - Brainstorming
 - Gallery walk
 - Post-Up
 - Affinity Map
 - Individually
 - Voting techniques
- Agenda
- Documents
- NN interactions
- National Workshops assessment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Documents

1. Presentations

How to make a good presentation?

- The simpler, the better →
 - Try placing important points in bullet points.
 - Figures or tables better than text
- Create an structure as if you were part of the audience →
 - Ask yourself what is the best order
 - Give a narrative to your presentation
- Use visual aids →
 - Incorporate photos or videos
- Design →
 - Do not use blocks of text
 - Use a minimalistic background
 - Maintain a consistent font style and size
- 10-20-30 rule →
 - 10 slides, 20 minutes & font size 30

2. Documents

For the smooth functioning of a meeting, supporting documents must be prepared carefully.

Notice calling the meeting and agenda are the key elements prior to the meeting. Meeting minutes are essential after the meeting.

Supporting documents should be clear and easy to read, include graphs, tables and other elements to facilitate reading.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Content

- Tools for Meetings and Workshops
 - Group activities
 - Brainstorming
 - Gallery walk
 - Post-Up
 - Affinity Map
 - Individually
 - Voting techniques
- Agenda
- Documents
- **NN interactions**
- National Workshops assessment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

NN Interactions

It has to be achieved a high networking rate of the Oper8 Thematic Network, aiming at joining forces with other projects to better develop data development, knowledge reservoirs, communication and dissemination activities and multi-actor approach.

Considering this, NNOs must conduct a kind of desktop study, or NN+OG members survey, in order to find potential projects to collaborate on the aforementioned activities.

- Identification of synergies with other relevant projects (thematic networks, EU-projects, National projects).
- Identification of synergies with European and International Policy (Civil Dialogue Groups, EIP-AGRI (Focus Groups, Operational Groups).
- Identification of synergies with other relevant OGs.

Activity scales	Total	Minimum	Desirable	Outstanding
Synthesis	1750 AKIS actors reached 140 farmers 140 advisors	250 AKIS actors reached per NN 1 OG per country 20 farmers per country 20 advisors per country	300 AKIS actors reached per NN 2 OG per country 25 farmers per country 25 advisors per country	350 AKIS actors reached per NN 3 OG per country 30 farmers per country 30 advisors per country
Links with other projects	at least 3 per country connections with research projects and other EC services	at least 3 per country connections with research projects and other EC services	at least 4 per country connections with research projects and other EC services	at least 5 per country connections with research projects and other EC services

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Content

- Tools for Meetings and Workshops
 - Group activities
 - Brainstorming
 - Gallery walk
 - Post-Up
 - Affinity Map
 - Individually
 - Voting techniques
- Agenda
- Documents
- NN interactions
- **National Workshops assessment**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

National Workshops assessment

In order to Checking the meeting quality, a survey must be sent with regard to:

- Preparatory activities
- Meeting Place
- Documents provided
- Food
- Timing
- Field trip
- Agenda distribution
- Networking

All these items could me assessed by **rating from 1 to 5**, it should be included a **final open question in order to ask for suggestions and potential improvements.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

Thank you!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential
of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

IFV | Camille GUILBERT

NNOs Physical meeting
1-2 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

NN overview

Description

- Focused on viticulture : technical expertise of IFV
- Partners and participants will mainly come from South-West of France and Mediterranean area

Aims

- Create a dynamic within the network for generating exchanges about herbicide reduction topic between the different stakeholders
- Sharing through the technical documents for Oper8 network to all agricultural sectors (ACTA technical institutes network)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

NN overview

Actors through focus group, questionnaire release and workshops

- IFV : NNO + 2 experts specializing in cover crop and mechanical tools / robotics
- Chambers of Agriculture : mainly viticulture advisors but also agroecology advisors
- Farmers and winegrower's cooperative
- Research (on progress)
- Policy makers: Water Agency
- Industry representatives : not yet decided

Networking challenges

- Getting enough people involved (KPI 250)
- Keeping the people interested and participating
- Having the people using the technical tools (videos...)
- Reaching other agriculture sectors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER8

THANK YOU

NAME & ADDRESS

IFV Sud-Ouest
1920 Route de Lisle sur Tarn
81310 PEYROLE
FRANCE
+33563336262
Camille Guilbert

EMAIL ADDRESS

camille.guilbert@vignevin.com

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER8

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential
of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

ADAS | Lynn Tatnell

NNOs Physical meeting
1-2 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Electrophysical control of perennial weeds: AIM

- Evaluate new technology for perennial weed control in grassland
- Herbicides not all clover-safe so limits choice
- Herbicide application timing often sub-optimal if contractors required
- Do integrating methods improve control? Achieving IWM?
- No commercial kit available for grassland
- Sites deliberately chosen with very high dock numbers
- Sites were actively grazed/and or cut too
- Not assessed the economics of this system within the project scope

Electrophysical
control

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG Results

Treatment	Timings- <u>year two</u>	Treatment description
1	Mid-late April (T1) + (T2) 4-6 weeks later	<u>Electrical treatment x2</u> (T1 + T2)
2	T1, T2 and (T3)- a further 4-6 weeks after (late June)	<u>Electrical treatment X3</u> (T1 + T2 + T3)
3	Mid-late April (T1) + herbicide 4-6 weeks later	<u>Electrical treatment x1</u> (T1) followed by <u>conventional herbicide*</u> (T2)
4	Herbicide late May-early June + electrical late June	<u>Conventional herbicide*</u> (T2) followed by <u>Electrical treatment x1</u> (T3)
5	Optimal timing for dock growth stage (May-June)	<u>Conventional herbicide alone</u> (T2)
6		<u>Untreated control</u>

Plots 6 x 2m,
3 reps

Electrophysical
control

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Electrophysical control

Electrophysical control

Results

Target weed growth stage

Dock at treatment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG Results: Year two % dock ground cover

Site A 2021

Site N 2021

- Results are taken 4 and 8 weeks after the last treatment
- Variation between sites. Higher weed burden at Site N
- Site A – 3 electrical treatments equivalent to combined treatment or herbicide alone
- Site N- Docks large at treatment -herbicide performance was sub-optimal

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Electrophysical
control

Electrical weeding: Conclusions

- Electrically treating on **three timings** was very effective
- Can be equivalent to a herbicide application alone
- Re-growth issues- monitor carefully – large tap root with docks
- Tractor mounted system could be effective- bar on a quad bike?
- Must consider the economics of the system - running costs
- Promising as additional tool for dock management in grassland
- Benefit organic farmers or those requiring lower herbicide inputs
- Help to retain clover in the sward as it is more of a spot treatment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPERS

THANK YOU

NAME & ADDRESS

Lynn Tatnell

EMAIL ADDRESS

Lynn.Tatnell@adas.co.uk

TELEPHONE NUMBER

+44 7815864440

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential
of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

ADAS | Kevin Godfrey

NNOs Physical meeting
1-2 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Robotic inter-row weeding: AIM

- **Aim:** To analyse the use of computerised robotic weeders in small scale horticultural operations in South Wales.
- Compared to hand weeding to evaluate cost and time savings
- Test its suitability in horticultural crops (smaller scale systems)
- 2018- trialled Garford robocrop hoe (inter-row weeder) – lessons learnt of how to move forward- need precision planting, moisture, flatter surface
- 2021 – trialled a steketee camera steerage hoe (more successful- much quicker)

Robotic
inter-row
weeding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG overview

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

EIP project: Robotic weeding 2022

- Machinery will be in Pembrokeshire
- Crop of leeks just drilled April 2022
- Weeder compared to conventionally treated crop
- We will be testing a Steketee camera steerage hoe
- Weed assessments pre- and post treatment
- Assessment of speed of travel and efficacy
- Event proposed for summer 2022

OG Results

What about your outcomes?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG pictures etc.

Graphic content and miscellaneous

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

THANK YOU

NAME & ADDRESS

Kevin Godfrey

EMAIL ADDRESS

Kevin.Godfrey@adas.co.uk

TELEPHONE NUMBER

XXXX

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential
of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

IFV | Camille GUILBERT

NNOs Physical meeting
1-2 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG overview: the “zero herbicide” project to support winegrowing farms in the reduction of herbicide use

Timeline and framework

- Between 2015 and 2018
- Mainly viticulture, also fruit trees experiments
- Experimental work to try different combination of under row cover crops : sowed, planted, species, and needs for managing it -> challenges of under row cover crop in Mediterranean climate
- Talking about the growth period for cover crops under the row
- Mechanical weeding between the rows

Partners

- 5 partners among Chambers of Agriculture and IFV for viticulture, and 2 (now gathered in one) among experimental research centers for fruit trees
- Trials on experimental and real farms

Challenges

- Led by Xavier Delpuech, colleague from the Montpellier team, who does not work anymore on that topic
- The OG ended several years ago : the partners of the projects are not anymore the same people

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG Results

Technical and practical results about

- How to implement an under-row cover crop and how to manage it : technical report
- Technical choices
 - 20-30% of the soil covered with under-row cover crops
 - Possibility for inter-rows covering for deep soils : 1 out of 2 inter-rows => 70-80% of the soil covered but possible needs of fertilization
 - Full coverage not recommend for Mediterranean conditions
- Tools for managing the cover crops (for sowing for example) were not yet very well adapted
- Farmers are interested by the technique

Focus on some results

- Light drought in the soil in spring when the plants start growing
- No increased drought during summer with the cover-crop
- High yield loss for very superficial (thin) soil, no yield loss for deep soil
- Vigor/Strength can be affected by competition of cover crop but yet can get stable in the next years
- Reduced nitrogen rate impacting the fermentation process
- Interesting technique for a narrow covered lane under the row
- After 4-5 years, the spontaneous weeds take the advantage

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG

OG

Un réseau d'essais « espèces »

OG

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No 101060591

OPER8

THANK YOU

NAME & ADDRESS

IFV Sud-Ouest
1920 Route de Lisle sur Tarn
81310 PEYROLE
FRANCE
+33563336262
Camille Guilbert

EMAIL ADDRESS

camille.guilbert@vignevin.com

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER8

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential
of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

University of Pisa | Lorenzo Tramacere, Daniele Antichi

NNOs Physical meeting
1-2 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Centre for Agri-environmental Research “Enrico Avanzi” (CiRAA)

CiRAA is the largest agricultural experimental centre in Italy and one of the largest in Europe (**more than 500 ha of agricultural land plus 722 ha woodland**). CiRAA’s mission includes research, development and transfer of innovation. CiRAA mainly conducts on-station but also on-farm research and regularly organizes demonstration activities to involve local stakeholders in new developments and products. The main research topics of CiRAA includes low-input cropping systems, soil tillage, **cover crops**, crop protection and **non-chemical weed control**, **organic farming**, **agroecology**, **agricultural mechanisation**, animal husbandry, food quality, biomass and bioenergy, economic and environmental impact.

See more on: <https://youtu.be/iZOLzqzQ2js>

Facilities

- Field exp. and technical staff
- Chemical lab
- Meeting room

 This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

The Operational Group IoConciv

A new context for weed management in perennial crops

 This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

The Operational Group loConciv

Time line: 2020-2022

- A project to validate and promote an innovative crop system in vineyards and orchards

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

The Operational Group loConciv

Mechanical methods

Physical methods

Organic phytochemicals

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

The Operational Group loConciv

Cover crops, advantages:

- Reduce soil erosion;
- Soil fertility;
- Carbon sequestration;
- Reduce soil compaction;
- Reduce nitrate leaching;
- Water infiltration;
- Weed control;
- Biodiversity increasing;.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

The Operational Group loConciv

Trifolium subterraneum

- Self-sowing
- Geocarpism
- Autumn-spring cycle
- Soil cover as living and dead mulch
- BNF – N₂
- Var Antas, medium-late variety

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

The Operational Group IoConciv

ACTIONS IMPLEMENTED:

2 Conventional farms:

1. Azienda Agricola Gini (Cenaia – PI)
2. Azienda Agricola Bellesi (San Miniato - PI)

2 Organic farms:

1. Azienda Agricola Spazzavento (Ponsacco – PI)
2. Azienda Agricola Monterosola (Volterra – PI)

Tested strategies:

- (i) tilled control
- (ii) intra-row permanent cover + tilled inter-row;
- (iii) intra-row permanent cover + inter-row permanent cover

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

The Operational Group IoConciv

AIM: to validate and promote alternative ways to manage the inter-row and intra-row space in vineyards

INNOVATION: differentiated groundcover in inter-row and intra-row space (subterranean clover acting both as living and dead mulch)

RESULTS:

- later grape maturity, lower sugar content, higher N content in berries
- adequate weed control both in winter and in spring-summer (comparable with mechanical weed control)
- costs reduction for tillage and herbicide spray
- GHGs reduction
- C sequestration increase
- soil erosion reduction (estimated)
- herbicides leaching reduction (estimated)
- soil fertility improvement (in progress)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

The Operational Group loConciv
Podere Spazzavento farm

Trifolium biomass in spring

Trifolium in autumn self-sowing

The Operational Group loConciv
Podere Spazzavento farm

Trifolium dead mulch vs bare soil

The Operational Group IoConciv
Monterosola farm – clay soil (March 2021)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

THANK YOU

NAME & ADDRESS

LORENZO TRAMACERE
VIA DEL BORGHETTO 80, PISA, ITALY

EMAIL ADDRESS

lorenzo.tramacere@unipi.it

TELEPHONE NUMBER

0039 0502218935

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

USC | María Rosa Mosquera Losada
Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro

NNOs Training – Spain. Production of natural plant oils to act as herbicides in organic farming systems

01 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

Content

- Operational Group description
- Further steps: Aims and Challenges
- Potential Actors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Content

- **Operational Group description**
- Further steps: Aims and Challenges
- Potential Actors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Basis for the introduction of essential oils for the natural control of weeds in horticulture crops Operational Group: CONTECAD

Antonio Rigueiro Rodríguez*

Elvira A. Díaz Vizcaíno**

Lucía Torres García*

*Grupo de Investigación Sistemas Agroforestales

antonio.rigueiro@usc.es

lucia.torres@usc.es

myrosa.mosquera.losada@usc.es

**Grupo de Investigación de Botánica Aplicada

elvira.diaz@usc.es

Fondo Europeo Agrícola de
Desenvolvemento Rural:
Europa inviste no rural

Background

Roman Wall UNESCO Heritage 2000)

Sinthetic chemical products: Use limited

New alternatives: Environmental friendly

Natural herbicides: Alelopatic compounds (natural products).

Methodology

- A assay with 20 products in vitro (water extracted, essential oils/**hidrolates**) were tested for the main weed of the wall (*Parietaria judaica*, *Spergula arvensis*)
- Phytotoxicity bioassays were carried out

Knowledge transfer

PHASE I *In vitro* assay

Detecting the potenciality of the herbicide, bioassay in crop chamber under controlled conditions

PHASE II Field/Greenhouse verification Verifying the effectiveness of the product, experimental desing in small plots *in situ*

PHASE III Natural herbicides obtention

Production and formulation of new herbicides products (verification/comercialization)

SOME RESULTS..

Efficiency verification in different weeds

AE-1, AE-3, AE-4 > AE-2, higher of the observed in the H group, even in spite of the producto washing (in t_1 , 7 days after washing, and t_2 , 30 días after washing).

Next steps.....

PHASE III NATURAL HERBICIDES OBTENTION

Product elaboration

Destillation of **essential oils**

Hidrolates recovery

Formulation of the natural herbicide

Compound stability

Further testing

Testing in other weeds

Comercialization

Ecoinnovative agriculture

Technical recomendations

New product

Content

- Operational Group description
- Further steps: Aims and Challenges
- Potential Actors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Aims

Product commercialization

Increasing number of farmers adopting organic farming (nonchemical weeding) to fulfil the Farm to Fork ambition of having a rate of 25% organic farms by 2030.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Challenges

Regulatory

Adequate value chains elaboration

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Potential Actors

A list of actors already networking with the research group including in the following actors groups:

Farmers

Natural herbicide companies

Policy makers

Advisors

Researchers

Organic farmers

Network & Agroecology working groups

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

Thank you!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OPER 8

European Thematic Network for unlocking
the full potential of Operational Groups
on alternative weed control

Agricultural University of Athens | *Ilias Travlos*

NNOS MEETING

1-2 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

The challenges

- ❖ Farmers are reluctant to adopt non-chemical methods.
- ❖ Weed resistance
- ❖ Transfer technological advances to small scale farms
- ❖ High labor cost & environmental impact
- ❖ High costs of weed control in vegetables

The need

- ❖ Replace manual work with environmentally friendly systems

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG overview

Development of an innovative weed system in Greece

The aim of the Greek Operational Group (OG) is the development of an innovative system for mechanical weed control between rows, in fresh onion and broccoli crops. The innovative mechanical weed control system utilizes computational vision methods to identify planting lines, as well as the exact pacing between them.

OG Members :

- ❖ Agricultural University of Athens (coordinator)
- ❖ Tractorgps
- ❖ Zamidis
- ❖ Vegiday IKE
- ❖ MS farm
- ❖ Multi-Farm "Our Land"

TRACTOR
GPS

AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS
ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΚΟ ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ ΑΘΗΝΩΝ

ZAMIDIS
SINCE 1992

ms farm
We grow for you!

Vegiday

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG Solution

The system consists of:

- ❖ A digital camera (RGB Camera).

As the tractor moves through, the digital camera powers the software with field images in real time.

Figure 1: Images along the lines during the movement of the weeding machinery

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG Solution

The system consists of:

- ❖ A software

The software retrieves images from the digital camera, processes them in real time and identifies the planting lines, in order to instruct the actuator to determine the course of the tractor's accessory, through its hydraulic displacement, so that it always follows its lines. This is important because the planting rows are never perfectly aligned. With the proposed system, the accessory is hydraulically, and automatically shifted and high speeds could be achieved, without the driver having to control the course of the accessory machine.

Figure 2. Recognition of planting lines

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG Solution

The system consists of:

❖ Actuator

The actuator is instructed by the software regarding the position of the planting lines relative to the accessory and will automatically receive position correction information, in case the mechanical carving parts are not in full alignment with the gap of each planting line.

❖ Weeder

This particular product has been designed to meet the needs of densely planted crops. Its special construction combined with shock absorbers (oil) in each element, increases the speed in the field without losing contact with the ground and affecting the driver. In addition, it could accommodate three different types of rows: 6-row, 8-row and 12-row .

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Expected Outcomes

- ❖ Development of a low-cost system that automatically correct its course
- ❖ Modernization and automation of the production process, with the use of new technological means and methods
- ❖ Improvement of the quality of products, through the elimination of plant injuries during mechanical weeding
- ❖ Reduction of chemical pollution of natural resources and minimization of soil compaction on agricultural lands
- ❖ Reduction of labour

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG timeline

OPER 8

Development of an innovative weed system in Greece

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

www.oper-8.eu

OPER 8
Thank you for watching!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential
of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

Farmers Parliament | Inga Bērziņa

NNOs Physical meeting
1-2 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Latvian NN overview I

Description

Latvian National Network on alternative weed control is going to be developed and widened during Oper8 project

Aim

Establish a platform/community that share new information and best praxis in weed control as well as test and evaluate new products and technologies to gain real-life experience and evaluate solutions efficacy in Latvian agroclimatic conditions

NN

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Latvian NN overview II

Main actors

- Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies
- Other research bodies
- Farmers Parliament
- Other agriculture NGOs
- Individual farmers
- Extension service providers

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Latvian NN overview III

Activity plan:

- Communication with potential NN actors
- Carry out survey regarding weed control
- Distribution of information regarding weed control methods in connection Oper8 project and also from other sources
- Organization of demo days
- Widening network of farmers interested to test and demonstrate new products and technologies

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

Latvian NN overview IV

Planned communication channels:

- Media (radio, TV)
- Social media and Websites
- WhatsApp groups
- E-mail lists
- Seminars and Demo days
- ZSA Newsletter and Magazine

NN

 OPERS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

 OPER8

THANK YOU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential
of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

University of Pisa | Lorenzo Tramacere, Daniele Antichi

NNOs Physical meeting
1-2 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

NN overview

Description: NN for Italy

Aims: to set National Action Plan on reduced use of herbicides in vineyards, arable crops and field vegetables

NN

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

NN overview

Actors (to be selected):

farmers (three major crop groups, from at least Northern, Central and Southern of Italy),

farmers associations/cooperatives (Coldiretti, which was involved in the OG, plus CIA, Confagricoltura, Condifesa Lombardia, Girolomoni, Federbio),

advisors (SPEVIS for vineyards, CONAF, HORTA srl),

industry (technical mean suppliers –e.g. Terre dell'Etruria for Tuscany-, machinery builders –e.g., DONDI SpA, MASCHIO-GASPARDO, CLEMENS, MAITO-, crop and cover crop seed companies –ISEA, Sativa, Carla Import),

policy makers (regional level –one officer from phytosanitary service of at least one region from North, Centre and South of Italy: Tuscany, Emilia Romagna; national level – one representative from the Ministry of Agriculture),

NGOs (consumers associations, environmentalists associations –Legambiente-, SIF Foundation),

scientists (IWM specialists, SIRFI, GIRE)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

NN overview

Networking challenges: scaling up from local-based OG to national level, wide range of crops and pedoclimatic conditions, involvement of Ministry

Organisation: NN to be organized around multi-actor working groups (e.g., herbicide reduction in vineyards) according to specific tasks

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

THANK YOU

NAME & ADDRESS

LORENZO TRAMACERE
VIA DEL BORGHETTO 80, PISA, ITALY

EMAIL ADDRESS

lorenzo.tramacere@unipi.it

TELEPHONE NUMBER

0039 0502218935

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential
of Operational Groups on alternative weed control

Farmers Parliament | Inga Bērziņa, Iveta Grudovska

LBTU | Maksims Fiļipovičs, Jānis Jaško

NNOs Physical meeting
1-2 February 2023 | Lugo, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG

OG overview

• **Institute of Plant Protection Research «Agrihorts» of Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies**

- specialises in scientific and practical research in different areas of agriculture including weed control
- involved in international and state fund scientific projects
- actively cooperates state institutions, NGOs and farmers

• **Farmers Parliament (new OG member)**

- most active agriculture NGO representing all types of farmers in Latvia
- Information and training activities, demo and field days
- involved in international and state fund projects (ZSA DIH)
- wide range of dissemination channels in LV and EU

• **3 organic vegetable farms (and 2 additional for this project)**

• **Institute of Electronics and Computer Science (no active participation in Oper8 project)**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG previous project

PROBLEMS:

- Weeding is one of the main challenges and cost position especially in vegetable crops
- Manual labour is often used due to lack of appropriate technical means
- Problem is enhanced by the lack of seasonal workers
- Herbicides are not solution because of the type of crop (e.g. vegetables) or the type of farming (e.g. organic)

SOLUTIONS:

- Prototype of camera-based plant recognition solution has been developed
- Prototype of 4 wheel autonomous platform that recognize weeds and treat them with either laser or small-scale rotating hoe has been developed

OG

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG Plans in Oper8

Activity plans:

- Evaluate weeding methods from other partners and literature
- Improve own weeding solutions
- Promote alternative weeding methods through workshops, seminars, demonstrations and media

Dissemination channels:

- Farmers' parliament members
- National network (*to be created*)
- Extension service
- Scientific conferences
- Students
- Professional organisations
- Policy makers

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

OG in Oper8

Done within OPER8 project so far:

- Consultations and meetings between partners from Latvia in relation to NN, OG and tasks from WP1, WP2 & WP5
- a draft version of the survey was framed → suggestions and improvements from partners were collected & implemented → in cooperation with ADAS finalization of OPER8 survey
- starting to work on WP2, Task 2 – identification of particular farmers for the survey.

Introduction & information about the survey

2. Do you see yourself as a farmer or non-farmer?

- Farmer
- Non-farmer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

THANK YOU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

